

Pyramids, Meteorites and Circumpolar Stars, that is to say, the Meteoric Iron in Ancient Egyptian and Chinese Cultures

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Before the Iron Age, that is before the advent of iron smelting, the main source of the metal was meteoric iron. Here we propose a discussion about the use of this iron to make artifacts by people of ancient Egypt and China. For Egypt, we will report as the meteoric iron appeared, according to what writes Robert Bauval and Alan Alford, in the Pyramid Texts. It is also told that of iron was made one of the ritual tools used during the “opening of the mouth ceremony”, an ancient Egyptian ritual described in funerary texts. One of the shapes of this tool resembled the asterism of the circumpolar stars of the Big Dipper. The iron of Tutankhamun’s dagger and of the Kamil Crater will be discussed too. Then, we will consider China, where meteoric iron was forged onto the blades of bronze weapons. We will discuss also the Hongshan Culture, famous for its jade artifacts. Modern artifacts, defined as Hongshan iron meteorites, show asterisms (the Big Dipper and Cassiopeia) carved on them, but the literature that we will mention here, about this Chinese neolithic culture, is not stressing any use of meteorites. In any case, it is true that the Nine Stars of the Big Dipper have been represented by Neolithic China. For what concerns the meteorites, as in the ancient Egypt, people of China considered the heavens as the source of meteoric iron.

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When in 1925 the British archaeologist Howard Carter discovered Tutankhamun's tomb, he found within the king's burial equipment a dagger. The dagger has its blade made of iron. This iron is coming from a meteorite as it has been confirmed recently by means of a non-invasive X-ray technique [Comelli et al., 2016]. In fact, since the 1960s, the high nickel content in the metal has been guessed as featuring a meteoric origin of the iron [Bjorkman, 1973]. Moreover, no Egyptian archaeological evidence exists of iron smelting until the 6th century BC [Schultz, 2013]. Before the Iron Age, that is before the advent of iron smelting, the main source of the metal was meteoric iron, apart from the extremely rare telluric iron. The meteoric iron was used to make cultural objects, tools and weapons [Waldbaum, 1980], which were luxury objects too, because of the rarity of this material. Therefore, it is not surprising that, in the ancient Egypt “iron was very strongly associated with royalty and power” [Marchant, 2013].

Jo Marchant, mentioning a study published in *Meteoritics & Planetary Science* [Johnson et al., 2013], tells us that this research has explained “how ancient Egyptians obtained iron millennia before the earliest evidence of iron smelting in the region”, and that the study also hints that Egyptians “regarded meteorites highly as they began to develop their religion”. “The sky was very important to the ancient Egyptians,” says Joyce Tyldesley, an Egyptologist at the University of Manchester, UK, and also that what was falling from the sky was “going to be considered as a gift from the gods” [Marchant, 2013]. Consequently, we can tell that a dagger with a meteoric iron blade was a dagger fit for a king, that is, the best gift for a king too.

Recently, in February 2022, it has been proposed that the dagger found in the Tutankhamun's tomb was a royal gift from a neighboring kingdom to the king of Egypt [Matsui et al., 2022]. However, as we will see, the iron of the blade seems being identified as that of the Kharga Oasis meteorite, then of Egyptian origin.

Here we propose a discussion about meteoric iron in ancient Egypt and China. For Egypt, we will start reporting how the iron is appearing in the Pyramid Texts. Then, besides discussing the iron of Tutankhamun’s dagger and other ancient items, we will search for its origin in the land of Egypt, remembering the recent discovery of Kamil Crater, a crater created by an iron meteorite. We will also see that some scholars have linked this iron from the sky to the circumpolar stars of the Big Dipper.

Through the Mughal Empire, we will pass from Egypt to China and its blades made of meteoric iron too. We will see that in China the meteoric iron was forged onto the blades

of bronze weapons.

For what concerns the meteorites, as in the ancient Egypt, people of China considered the heavens as the source of meteoric iron. We will consider in particular the Hongshan jades and meteorites. Modern artifacts, defined as Hongshan iron meteorites, show asterisms (the Big Dipper and Cassiopeia) carved on them, but the literature that we will mention here, about the neolithic Hongshan culture, is not stressing any use of meteorites. In any case, we will see that it is true that the Nine Stars of the Big Dipper - nine, not seven - have been represented by Neolithic China.

Sidereus Nuncius

“Sidereus Nuncius” means Sidereal Messenger, or The Starry Messenger. This is the title of a short astronomical treatise by Galileo Galilei, published in 1610. Galileo was proposing the first scientific work based on observations made by means of a telescope. In it, we find the Medicean Stars, that are circling Jupiter and that had been later defined by Kepler as the Jupiter satellites [Sparavigna, 2016].

We are remembering the title of Galileo’s work, because it contains a Latin adjective - sidereus – which is coming from sidus, sider- ‘star’. And meteorites look like Starry Messengers indeed.

In [wiktionary](#), etymology tells to compare “sidus” with Ancient Greek σίδηρος (sídēros). “Some derive this from Proto-Indo-European sweid-, whence Latin sūdor, Greek ἰδρώς (hidrós), English sweat”. Moreover, in [wiktionary.org](#) it is told that etymology of the Greek term is “unclear and debated. One view compares it with Latin sīdus (“constellation, meteorite”), with this possibly related to Proto-Indo-European sweyd- (“to sweat”), whence Latin sūdor (“sweat, moisture”), Ancient Greek ἰδρώς (hidrós, “sweat, perspiration”), English sweat. Another theory compares it with Udi zido (“iron”), indicating a Northeast Caucasian loanword. Finally, the word is very likely of Pre-Greek origin given its semantics, which has been compared with Ancient Greek σίδη (sídē, “pomegranate”), linked to the reconstruction sida "red" thereby giving the meaning of σίδηρος (sídēros) as "red metal" (perhaps in relation to its red oxide ores and minerals)". No references, in particular about the Pre-Greek origin, are given. In any case, it seems that we are ranging from the sweat (of the sky?) to the color of the metal.

Now, let us consider an Egyptian hieroglyphic sign. It is defined as the sign N41 in the Gardiner's sign list.

Sign N41 and the Pyramid Texts

“Ancient Egyptians saw the sky as crumbling iron tub filled with water”, it is told by New Scientist [Barras, 2020]. This is the title of news reporting about a study of philology

[Almansa-Villatoro, 2019], which is concerning a sign considered as representing “iron” in Egypt. In [Almansa-Villatoro, 2019], about the Egyptian hieroglyphic sign N41, it is told that it was used in a "constellation of words related to women, water and metals".

N41 U+1321E	well with ripple of water	ḥmt bj³	Phonemes for <i>ḥmt</i> , <i>bj³</i> ; A "basin", but commonly used for 'wife', or 'woman'
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https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/List_of_Egyptian_hieroglyphs#N

The symbolic meaning of iron has a consistent relation with the sky in religious texts. The "Egyptian cosmovision contemplated the sky as an iron container of water, pieces of which fell to the earth in the shape of meteors and were used to produce ritual objects. The indexicality of the N41 sign suggests that the relation between birth, afterlife, and iron existed even before the first attested long religious texts in Egypt. Finally, the lexical parallels between Egypt and Mesopotamia can be explained as a common reaction to the phenomena of falling iron meteorites", tells the author of [Almansa-Villatoro, 2019].

The meteoric iron was previously considered as the "Iron of Creation" [Alford, 2010] and that of the "Iron Eggshell" [Alford, 2004], in the titles of two books by Alan F. Alford, British writer and speaker that worked on ancient religion, mythology, and Egyptology. Looking at N41, after reading the title of Alford' book of 2004, we could see in it a broken eggshell too. And pieces of this eggshell, sometimes, were coming down from it in the form of meteorites. Coming from the vault of the sky populated by stars and gods, these pieces, besides being rare, were precious relics of the sky. Alan Alford proposed that the sarcophagus in the King's Chamber in the Great Pyramid of Giza, that is the pyramid of king Khufu, was actually used to enshrine iron meteorites [Alford, 2010, 2004],[W-Alford]. Alford, referring to the Pyramid Texts, guesses that this iron was put into the sky at the time of creation, “according to the Egyptians’ geocentric way of thinking. The King's Chamber, with its upward inclined dual ‘airshafts’, was built to capture the magic of this mythical moment" [W-Alford].

Let us remember that the Pyramid Texts are the oldest ancient Egyptian funerary texts, dating to the late Old Kingdom. These texts were carved onto the subterranean walls and sarcophagi of pyramids at Saqqara from the end of the Fifth Dynasty, and throughout the Sixth Dynasty of the Old Kingdom, and into the Eighth Dynasty of the First Intermediate Period. Khufu was the second pharaoh of the Fourth Dynasty, in the first half of the Old Kingdom period.

Dynasty	Seat	Period of rule			Rulers		
		Start	End	Term	First to rule	Last to rule	List / Family tree
Old Kingdom							
Dynasty III	Memphis	2687 BC	2613 BC	73 years	Djoser	Huni	(list)
Dynasty IV	Memphis	2613 BC	2494 BC	112 years	Sneferu	Shepseskaf or Thamphthis ^[a]	(list) _____ (tree)
Dynasty V	Memphis	2494 BC	2345 BC	149 years	Userkaf	Unas	(list)
Dynasty VI	Memphis	2345 BC	2181 BC	164 years	Teti	Merenre Nemtyemsaf II or Netjerkare Siptah ^[b] or Nitocris ^[c]	(list)

Old Kingdom. Table from https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Dynasties_of_ancient_Egypt

Bja (Robert Bauval)

“In 1989 I [Bauval] published an article in the Oxford periodical *Discussions in Egyptology* in which I [Bauval] reviewed the nature and origin of the Benben Stone and its powerful connection with the pyramid cult. ... Also there had been hints by the Egyptologists Wallis Budge and Jean-Philippe Lauer that the Benben Stone was likely to have been a sacred meteorite akin to the so-called ‘Black Stone’ of the Muslims kept encrusted on the wall of the Ka’ba shrine at Mecca in Saudi Arabia. ... [Bauval] was naturally very intrigued to find out that in the Pyramid Texts there were numerous references to the ‘bones’ of the dead kings being made of a substance called ‘bja’ which Egyptologists translated as ‘iron’: *I am pure, I take to myself my iron bones, I stretch out my imperishable limbs ... My bones are iron and my limbs are the imperishable stars ... the (dead) king’s bones are iron, and his limbs are the imperishable stars ...* . Now equating the ‘bones’ of dead kings to ‘iron’ does not make much sense until one realises that the transfigured body of a departed monarch was imagined to become a ‘star’: *The king is a star ... The king appears as a star ... Behold, the king arises as this star ... [O king] be a soul like a living star ...* Even today, the streaking of a meteorite across the dark sky is often referred to as a ‘falling star’ or ‘shooting star’” [Bauval, 1999]. In the Appendix 1 of the Bauval’s book, 1999, we can find detailed discussion about meteoric iron. However, we can find told by Bauval that “A few Egyptologists have recently questioned the Bja = iron for the Old Kingdom epoch, suggesting ‘copper’ instead; see A. Nibbi, *JARCE* xiv, 1977, p.59; C. Lalouette, *BIFAC* 79, p.67. Nonetheless, Bja is widely

accepted as being iron, and especially meteoritic iron in archaic times”.

Bja (Alan Alford)

As we have seen before, the hieroglyphic sign N41 is rendered by bꜣ, phonetic bja.

In the Chapter 10 of *The Midnight Sun*, 2004, Alford is telling that we have in the Pyramid texts the ubiquitous presence of a substance called *bja*. Alford writes that this word is usually translated ‘iron’. The *ka*¹ of the king “lifts up his bones of bja, splits open his egg of bja, sits on his throne of bja, splits or traverses the bja of the sky, comes to rest on ropes of bja with which the sky-barque is towed, and exits the sky through doors of bja”. And the theme continues in the Coffin Texts. And Alford mentions them.

Let us assume that the meaning is ‘iron’ and not ‘metal - and we will see that this translation has been proposed too - the relevant question is the following. Why is bja important? And, according to Alford, “What is the meaning of this? Why are the Egyptian texts littered with references to iron?” According to E. A. Wallis Budge (1904), the sky comprised a slab of iron resting upon four pillars. Alford is also mentioning James P. Allen, who theorized that of bja was made the basin containing the waters of sky: “one way or another, the consensus is that the iron was one of the materials of which the sky was made”.

Akhet Khufu

About the Great Pyramid, in [W-Alford] it is also told that it was interpreted by Alford "as a network of secret chambers in which religious relics were concealed – hence the title of his book *Pyramid of Secrets*". Ref. W-Alford, Wikipedia on Alford, stresses that this is "the weakest part of his case, as the textual support for the idea is thin and there is no way of knowing what might have been contained in the chambers that we know of today" [W-Alford], [Fortean Times Magazine]. "Alford's theory can be proven or negated by future exploration, since it is central to his case that further secret chambers exist. In this regard, his thoughts are guided by the scholar J.P. Lepre, who claimed that anomalous patterns in the Pyramid's masonry joints might be signs to the existence of hidden passages and chambers" [W-Alford].

Alford also proposed a role of sound in air-shafts of the pyramid. “The second key component of the re-enactment was meteoritic iron – the seed of creation – which was hermetically sealed inside the King’s Chamber sarcophagus... In a symbolic sense, the sound spiritualised the iron and ejected it into the northern and southern skies, via the shafts, thereby re-enacting the formation of the celestial bodies: the circumpolar stars in

¹About *ka* see please <https://www.britannica.com/topic/ka-Egyptian-religion>

the northern sky, and the Sun, the Moon, and the rising-and-setting stars in the southern sky (in Egyptian myth, all of these bodies were said to be made of iron). The King's Chamber was therefore a 'chamber of creation', in keeping with the creational symbolism of the Pyramid, as illustrated in the diagram to the right". This is told by Alford at https://old.world-mysteries.com/alford_GP.htm

In [Alford, 2010], it is stressed that the name of the Great Pyramid is *Akhet Khufu*. However, "*Akhet* did not refer simply to 'the horizon', but rather to 'the land of spiritual light' – the proto-earth in its process of spiritual transformation". Then, *akhet* was not simply the horizon "upon which the Sun rose every day, but rather the primeval earth from which all of the celestial bodies had risen at the beginning of time, initially in the form of spiritualised iron seed".

Akhet Khufu "is therefore to be translated 'Khufu's island (or mountain) of spiritual light', a name" which contains in it the king, the pyramid and the creator-god [W-Alford].

Hong-Quan Zhang, 2023, has investigated the Akhet environment, as we can find depicted by the Pyramid Texts, comparing it with the local hydrology during the Green Sahara time. As Zhang tells in the abstract, "The Pyramid Texts contain vivid, specific, and consistent details of the Akhet and its surrounding lakes, canals, and farmlands." Using a climate change approach and hydrological profiles of the Green Sahara time, Zhang's "insight provides a key to decipher many obscure words in the current English translations. It also helps pinpoint the scattered environmental descriptions in the Pyramid Texts into a coherent portrait". The article "examines the relevant original hieroglyphs in the Pyramid Texts against their corresponding transliterations and English translations".

The Crested Ibis

Zhang writes that there are two manners of writing Akhet, one contains the hieroglyph of the Crested Ibis , Gardiner's list N27. Zhang notes that Akhet "is generally translated as "horizon" which blanks its original true identification.

So we have two hieroglyphs used for Akhet. Let us stress that the name of the Cheops' pyramid is written with the Crested Ibis. See please the detailed discussion in my:

[The Egyptian Hieroglyph of the Crested Ibis, from the Cheops' pyramid \(Akhet Khufu\) to the Akhenaten's Glory of Aten.](#) Zenodo, 2015.

Zhang tells also: "The Pyramid Texts portray the Akhet as the gate between the Duat and the Sky, a focal point of the ancient Egyptian religion. It is the place where the deceased becomes akh with the Sun. His akh will rise from the Akhet with the gods to the Sky (PT217:3-4). The afterlife includes a journey through the Field of Reeds to join the gods,

specifically the Ennead from Heliopolis and their associates, exclusive of gods from other cults. Then, the deceased experiences a perpetual rebirth everyday with the Sun at the Akhet."

As previously told, in Zhang, 2023, we can find two signs for the word "Akhet". Therefore, we can ask ourselves, what is the sign used in the Pyramid Texts?

Akhet in the Gardiner list N27 resembles the sun between two hills. Robert Bauval (Academia.edu) tells that, looking at sign N27, Mark Lehner in 1985 wrote: *[a] dramatic effect is created at sunset during the summer solstice as viewed, again, from the eastern niche of the Sphinx Temple. At this time, and from this vantage, the sun sets almost exactly midway between the Khufu and Khafre pyramids, thus construing the image of the Akhet, 'Horizon', hieroglyph on a scale of acres*". Bauval continues saying that, "however, a fatal flaw [exists] with this idea: the hieroglyphic sign of the 'sun disk between two mountains' did not exist when Khufu built his pyramid! And even if it did, it was not used in the writing of the name 'Akhet Khufu'. In 1997 Lehner did acknowledge this fact: *Khufu's pyramid was Akhet Khufu. Here, and in the Pyramid Texts, Akhet is written with the crested-ibis and elliptical land-sign, not with the hieroglyph of the sun disk between two mountains that was used later to write 'horizon'.*"

Robert Bauval also adds: "In fact sign N27 is not found in the Pyramid Texts, where the word 'Akhet' is written with the crested-ibis sign G25, and the elliptical land-sign N18. The same applies for the word 'Akhet' in the name 'Akhet Khufu', where 'Akhet' is also written with the crested-ibis sign G25 and elliptical land-sign N16". ***In Akhet Khufu, as written at the time of Cheops, the elliptical land-sign is NOT used. See all details in my [Sparavigna, 2025](#).***

Bauval continues: "Amazingly, this mistake in interpretation of the name of the Great Pyramid is still found in recently published book. To be fair, Lehner [in his *The Complete Pyramids*, 1997, p. 29] did recognize that 'Akhet' --- although erroneously translated as 'horizon' in many books --- is written with the crested-ibis that also denotes the word Akh, meaning a 'spirit' who lives in the Duat (afterworld), the latter often written with a star in a circle". Bauval continues saying that Lehner offered another meaning for 'Akhet Khufu', that is, *the place where the deceased (king Khufu) becomes an Akh, a suggested translation is "Spirit" or "Light" Land.*" According to James P. Allen, an expert on the Pyramid Texts, "The Axt (Akhet) is the place in which the king, like the sun and other celestial beings, undergoes the final transformation from the inertness of death and night to the form that allows him to live effectively - that is as an akh - in his new world. It is for this reason that the king and his celestial companions are said to "rise from the Axt (Akhet)," and not because the Axt (Akhet) is a place on the horizon or - as some have suggested - because it is a place of light.' Akhet, therefore, must mean the 'Place of Becoming Akh'...". This is the interpretation provided by J.P. Allen, as reported by Robert Bauval.

Fig.1 : The land and the pyramids in a topographic map provided by the web site <https://it-ch.topographic-map.com>. Many thanks to Yamazaki D., D. Ikeshima, R. Tawatari, T. Yamaguchi, F. O'Loughlin, J.C. Neal, C.C. Sampson, S. Kanae & P.D. Bates, 2017, [Yamazaki et al., 2017], for their fundamental work on digital elevation data and models, and many thanks to the excellent web site, which is fundamental for the maps. topographic map helps understanding the local environment of Akhet Khufu.

“The story that I am about to tell is as strange as it is controversial. It is the story of an age-long mystery. A mystery which has haunted the imaginations of seekers from generation to generation. A mystery which has, in recent years, split the archaeological establishment and has caused debate around the world. To some it is a figment of the imagination, a myth without historical basis. To others it is an obvious possibility, a near-certain historical reality, a fact that will soon be confirmed at the turn of a spade. For deep inside the oldest, the largest, the tallest, the most tremendous and sacred monument on this planet, is a heavily guarded secret. Inside the Great Pyramid of Giza, wrapped in unearthly darkness and standing in hallowed stillness, could lie a secret chamber, waiting any minute now to be opened.” (R. Bauval, 1999)

The big void in Akhet Khufu

Alan Alford passed away in 2011. In November 2017, it has been announced that the Great Pyramid of Giza is containing a hidden void, at least a hundred feet long. "The space's dimensions resemble those of the pyramid's Grand Gallery, the 153-foot-long, 26-foot-tall corridor that leads to the burial chamber of Khufu, the pharaoh for whom the pyramid was built. However, it remains unclear what lies within the space, what purpose it served, or if it's one or multiple spaces" [Greshko, 2017]. The Great Pyramid was built during the reign of Khufu (Cheops) of the fourth dynasty. The reign lasted from 2509 BC to 2483 BC. To understand its internal structure, as detailed in [Morishima et al., 2017], muons, which are by-products of cosmic rays that are only partially absorbed by stone, have been used. "The resulting cosmic-ray muon radiography" allowed the authors of [Morishima et al., 2017], "to visualize the known and any unknown voids in the pyramid in a non-invasive way".

Are, in this - single or multiple - void, "sacred artefacts" or relics as given in the framework of Alford's theory? Let us remember once more Alan Alford, who told the sacred artifacts "concealed in the secret chambers, including iron meteorites in the King's Chamber sarcophagus". The pyramid was a time capsule full of objects that, for the most part, were intended for a future generation, for people able to "unseal the hidden passages to access the secret vaults". Grand Gallery, Queen's Chamber and King's Chamber were robbed of their contents in antiquity, and then deprived of their religious relics concealed in them [Alford, 2010]. And some sacred artifacts were made of iron too, like the "bones" of the king, as we will see in the following of our discussions (see "Shafts and Heaven's Doors" section).

In the secret repository

"When a Horus-king died, he was assured a rebirth with Osiris, that is to say he became at one with Osiris in the afterworld of the Duat – his astral self being transported to Sirius or Orion through the energies of the Pyramid and the elaborate ritual he was made to go through to achieve 'eternal life'. ... In the secret repository of the King's Chamber within the Great Pyramid the age-old tradition relates that the builders had placed 'instruments of iron, arms which rust not, glass which might be bended but not broken, and strange spells'. But what did the first explorers find after having tunneled their way into the secret chamber? The only furniture was a lidless, hollowed stone coffer, containing not a body but a layer of a mysterious powdery substance. ... 100% *platinum-group* compound. The King's Chamber was, therefore, apparently contrived as a superconductor, capable of transporting the pharaoh into another dimension of space-time – and it was here that his Rite of Passage was administrated in accordance with the Book of the Dead." [Farley, 2011].

Here a comment is necessary. In Physics, the term “superconductor” has a specific meaning. Its use for the King’s Chamber is odd. To become a superconductor, a material needs low temperatures. Superconductivity at room temperature has been obtained at high pressure.

“In 2020, scientists claimed the first evidence of room temperature superconductivity at roughly 15 degrees Celsius (59 degrees Fahrenheit). Now another group of researchers claims to have achieved hot superconductivity at roughly 282 C (541 F), more than hot enough to pop corn, research they detailed online March 4 in the journal *Frontiers in Electronic Materials*. ... Both the claims of room temperature and hot superconductivity involve extremely high pressures, which apparently help superconductivity occur despite the high temperatures. For instance, room temperature superconductivity reportedly appeared at 267 gigapascals, more than 2,400 times the pressure at the bottom of the Mariana Trench, the deepest point in the ocean” [Choi, 2022].

In any case, as told in [Raub, 1984], “Even extra purified palladium and platinum are not superconducting. The lowest test temperature published is 0.1 K but according to a private communication from A. C. Mota neither palladium nor platinum are superconducting, even if checked at temperatures as low as $10 \times 10^{-3} \text{K}$ ”. For more details, see please Ref. [Raub, 1984].

“Superconductors are materials that, when cooled below a certain temperature, allow electricity to travel through them without any resistance. ... Researchers are constantly on the lookout for inexpensive new materials that can become superconducting at higher temperatures than currently possible” [MaterialsToday, 2016]. “A team of researchers from Hokkaido University, along with colleagues at the Kyushu Institute of Technology, NEC Corporation, Keio University and the National Institute for Materials Science, have now developed a novel superconducting material based on platinum. They have managed to do this even though until recently platinum was not thought to have superconducting properties” [MaterialsToday, 2016, Fujioka et al., 2016]. The novel material is made by mixing lanthanum (La), platinum (Pt) and arsenic (As) powders in a ratio of 1:5:1. “At a pressure of 5GPa (gigapascals) – equivalent to 50,000 bars of pressure – this process produced a non-superconducting form of LaPt5As, but at 10GPa it produced a superconducting form, with another non-superconducting form at 15GPa”. Therefore, it is true that recently a material which is containing platinum displayed superconductivity, but it happens at very high pressure.

“Recent superconductor experiments have often focused on high pressures because previous research suggested that metallic hydrogen, which theoretically forms at pressures as high as nearly 500 gigapascals, is a room temperature superconductor. Given how extremely difficult metallic hydrogen is to create, superconductor researchers have instead explored compounds rich in hydrogen. They conjecture the other elements in these compounds may compress the hydrogen atoms within these materials to help

superconductivity occur at pressures lower than those needed with metallic hydrogen” [Choi, 2022]. Actually, in 2018, superconductivity at roughly minus 13 C was obtained with lanthanum hydride at 150 Gpa. For palladium hydride, see [Kawae et al. 2020].

Whatever it is

We have seen that the vault of heavens was imagined like a container made of *bja* (*bia*) The translation of *bja* was “iron”, specifically “meteoric iron”. However, and we will show it, the term *bja* is also rendered in “metal”, “copper”, and “hematite”. Therefore, the word *bja* can refer to a hard and dense material, by means of which tools and containers could have been made.

Alford imagined that the King’s Chamber contained relics from heavens, the meteoric *bja*. And he also proposed the existence of other secret chambers in which religious relics were concealed. Following Alford, can we imagine them in the *void* in Akhet Khufu? Whatever they are, the base assumption is that the void is a secret chamber or vault. However, as told in [Hoare, 2020], a structural engineer, Peter James, described the ancient Egyptian construction technique of pyramids telling that, besides the larger blocks of foundation, out-side layer and internal ramps, smaller blocks had been used inside it [Construction Specifier, 2018]. With the use of smaller stones, “you will get many of these [voids]” inside. And Dr Zahi Hawass, concerning the news of the big void detected by means of muons, tells that “The pyramid is full of voids and that does not mean there is a secret chamber or a new discovery” [Frontier Post, 2018].

Fig.2 - English: Inner structure of the Great Pyramid of Khufu, Deutsch: Innere Struktur der Cheops-Pyramide, Français : Coupe et distribution interne de la grande pyramide de Khéops à Gizeh, Русский: Поперечный разрез пирамиды Хеопса, Date 30 December 2015, Source Own work based on: Cheops-Pyramide.png, Courtesy Author Юкатан for Wikimedia -Descriptions had been added on the image.

Caliph Al Ma'mun and his father

In the previous Figure 2 showing what had been found inside the pyramid, it is possible to see a “robber’s tunnel”. Then, who has explored the pyramid in the past?

“In the seventh century AD, the Rashidun Caliphate conquered Egypt, ending several centuries of Romano-Byzantine rule. A few centuries later, in 820 AD, the Abbasid Caliph Al-Ma'mun (786–833) is said to have tunneled into the side of the structure and discovered the ascending passage and its connecting chambers.” [Wikipedia](#)

Mike Dash in his “Inside the Great Pyramid”, 2011, is providing a detailed discussion. “The evidence that the Great Pyramid was similarly plundered is more equivocal; the accounts we have say two quite contradictory things. They suggest that the upper reaches of the structure remained sealed until they were opened under Arab rule in the ninth century AD. But they also imply that when these intruders first entered the King's Chamber, the royal sarcophagus was already open and Khufu's mummy was nowhere to be seen. This problem is one of more than merely academic interest, ... Given that, it's important to know what was written by the various antiquaries, travelers and scientists who visited Giza before the advent of modern Egyptology in the 19th century”.

Article [Dash, 2011] continues explaining that the pyramid possesses two distinct tunnel systems. The lower one corresponds to those found in earlier monuments; the upper, “which was carefully hidden and perhaps survived inviolate much longer”, “is unique to the Great Pyramid”. After references to Herodotus and Strabo, Dash tells that “It is not until we reach the 800s, and the reign of an especially curious and learned Muslim ruler, the Caliph Ma'mun, that the record becomes interesting again. *It's here that it becomes necessary to look beyond the obvious.* Most scholarly accounts state unequivocally that it was Ma'mun who first forced his way into the upper reaches of the pyramid, in the year 820 A.D.”

Ref. [Dash, 2011] stresses that the Arab chronicles are “collections of legends and traditions needing interpretation. Indeed, the earliest, written by the generally reliable al-Mas'udi and dating to no earlier than c. 950, does not even mention Ma'mun” but “attributes the breaching of the pyramid to Ma'mun's father, Haroun al-Rashid, ... When, the chronicler writes, after weeks of labor Haroun's men finally forced their way in, they found a vessel filled with a thousand coins of the finest gold, each of which was a dinar in weight. ... Al-Idrisi, writing in 1150, says that the caliph's men uncovered both ascending and descending passages, plus a vault containing a sarcophagus which, when opened, proved to contain ancient human remains. But other chroniclers of the same period tell different and more fantastical tales. One, Abu Hamid, the Andalusian author of the *Tuhfat al Albab*, insists ... that those who went up there in the time of Ma'mun came to a small passage, containing the image of a man in green stone, which was taken out for examination before the Caliph; when it was opened a human body was discovered in golden armor, decorated with precious stones, and in his hand was a sword of inestimable

value, and above his head a ruby the size of an egg, which shone like fire” [Dash, 2011].
A sword, or a meteoric iron dagger?

Shafts and Heaven’s Doors

Let us consider again the Pyramid Texts. “As discussed in chapter ten [Alford, 2004], iron (*bja*) is ubiquitous in the Pyramid Texts. The deceased king as Osiris has his mouth split open with an adze of iron, and resurrects himself by lifting up his iron bones, splitting open his iron egg, splitting or traversing the iron in the sky, and sitting on his iron throne.” “*O king! Raise yourself, receive your head, gather your bones together, shake off your dust, and sit on your iron throne*”, tells Alford reporting the Pyramid Texts, adding that in sitting upon the iron throne, the king acquires power over the gods - ‘those whose seats are hidden’ – and the king “becomes the master of his own resurrection”. “*Sit on this iron throne, give commands to those whose seats are hidden. The doors of the sky are opened for you*” [Alford 2010, 2004]. This is a passage of the resurrection of the King in the Pyramid Texts. What are these doors? Are doors existing in the Great Pyramid?

Rowan Hooper (2011) wrote for the New Scientist that Akhet Khufu “is thought to have been built as a tomb for the pharaoh Khufu, ... It contains three main chambers: the Queen’s Chamber, the Grand Gallery and the King’s Chamber, which has two air shafts connecting it with the outside world. Strangely, though, there are two tunnels, about 20 centimetres by 20 centimetres, that extend from the north and south walls of the Queen’s Chamber and stop at stone doors before they reach the outside of the pyramid”. The author is also telling that the “function of these tunnels [shafts] and doors is unknown, but some believe that one or both could lead to a secret chamber. Several attempts have been made to explore the tunnels using robots. In 1993, a robot crawled some 63 metres up the tunnel in the south wall and discovered what appeared to be a small stone door set with metal pins. Metal is not part of any other known structure in the pyramid, and the discovery ignited speculation that the pins were door handles, keys or even parts of a power supply constructed by aliens”. Metal pins are made of copper, as told in [Hawass, 2003].

Doors are therefore in shafts of the pyramid, those from the Queen’s Chamber.

“I believe – Dr Zahi Hawass tells in his “The Secret Doors Inside the Great Pyramid”, 2003 - that the shafts from the so-called Queen’s Chamber likely have no function, as they were blocked from the inside. If they had a religious function, they should have been left open, as were the shafts of the third burial chamber (the King’s Chamber). Since these open outside of the pyramid, I believe that Khufu’s soul was meant to travel through them. The south shaft was intended for Khufu to use as the sun god Ra. ... The north shaft was made for the soul of Khufu as Horus to travel to the stars in order to emerge from them as the sun god”. *The doors of the sky are opened for you.*

Fig. 3 - Diagram of the Great Pyramid, 2007. a work Courtesy by Jeff Dahl. On the diagram, the void has been added as depicted by The Times, (Whipple, 2007) - From [Bauval and Gilbert, 1994]: “The northern shafts, like the two that point south, are set meridionally. However, unlike their southern counterparts the northern shafts have a rather curious ... "anomaly" that has long puzzled Egyptologists and, recently, Rudolf Gantenbrink who explored them in 1992-3. During a conference given, on the 21 June 1993 ... he reminded the Egyptologists present that when he guided his robot up the northern shafts he came across the junction where they meet up with the Grand Gallery Because of the Grand Gallery's structural elements being in the direct path of the shafts, these had to be given a wide "kink" to the west of their meridional direction in order to by-pass the structural obstacle”. Is the shaft passing through the void or by-passing it?

Alan Alford tells, in his book of 2010, that “consensus has formed around the view that the shafts of the King’s chamber had a religious purpose. Connected with the despatch of king’s soul to the sky”. Alford does not agree. An immediate objection to the soul-shaft theory is that the king’s soul can pass through solid masonry, according to Egyptian religion. Moreover, only the Great Pyramid had shafts. “Why would Khufu alone, among all the kings of the pyramid age, have felt it necessary to build hollow shafts via which his soul might ascend to the heavens?” [Alford, 2010].

Metal pins of the shaft door are made of copper, and this is the only metal that had been discovered in Akhet Khufu.

A63

U+13048

king on throne

holding staff

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/List_of_Egyptian_hieroglyphs#A

Suggested further reading: *The Opening Of The Mouth Ceremony And The Northern Shafts In Cheops's Pyramid*, by R. G. Bauval and A.G. Gilbert , available in *Discussions in Egyptology* 28, 1994 [Bauval and Gilbert, 1994]. In this reference, it is proposed a very interesting discussion about the air shafts in the pyramid.

Iron throne and sceptre

“The iron throne (khndu bjai) is mentioned twenty times in the Pyramid Texts” [Alford, 2004], and Alford gives the passages in the notes according to translations by Faulkner/Eyre/Alford or Faulkner/Alford [Faulkner, 1969, Eyre, 2002]. “The king is said to sit on it, whereupon he is giving offering of meat and jars of purifying water. While seated on the iron throne, the king governs, judges, and gives orders to the gods – both the gods in the *duat* (those whose seats are hidden) and the gods in the sky (the spirits, the imperishable stars). His symbols of authority are the mace and the sceptre, the latter allegedly being made of iron.” [Alford, 2004]. Then, besides the throne, also the sceptre was made of iron, meteoric iron.

“The iron throne is a place from which the dead are far removed. To reach it, the king must reassemble his body and rise from the tomb. This process is described in Utterances 413 and 536: *Awake, O king, raise yourself, receive your head, gather your bones together, shake off your dust, and sit on your iron throne. ... Raise yourself, loose your bonds, throw off your dust, sit on this your iron throne ...* The iron throne is a thing ‘at which the gods marvel’. It has faces which are the faces of lions, and feet which are the hooves of the Great Wild Bull. To sit on this emblematic throne is to be ensured of an ascent to the sky, as numerous passages testify” [Alford, 2004]. “For example: *You will ascend to the sky as Horus upon the shedshed of the sky ... you being seated upon your iron throne ... Sit on this your iron throne, give commands to those whose seats are hidden. The doors of the sky are opened for you ... Sit upon your iron throne ... Run your course, row over your waterway like Re on the banks of the sky*” [Alford, 2024].

“In addition, the throne is said to possess a stairway, where the gods clap their hands when the king ascends to the sky. The king’s ascent in Utterance 483 is particularly intriguing: *The earth speaks, the gate of the earth-god is open, the doors of Geb are opened for you in your presence, and your speech goes up to Anubis ... May you remove your self to the sky upon your iron throne.*” [Alford, 2004] And the Alford’s discussion continues.

Utterances

Utterance 536 from the The Pyramid Texts, Translation by Samuel A. B. Mercer, 1952.

“To say: Thy water belongs to thee, thine abundance belongs to thee, thine efflux comes out of Osiris to thee. The double doors of heaven are open for thee; the double doors of Nut are open for thee; the double doors of heaven are open for thee; the double doors of ... are open for thee. "Welcome," says Isis; "(come) in peace," says Nephthys, when they see their brother. Raise thyself up; untie thy bandages; shake off thy dust. Sit thou upon this thy firm throne. Thou art pure with thy four nmś.t-jars and thy four 'ḡb.t-jars, which come for thee out of thy chapel of natron, which were filled for thee in the natron lake, and which Horus of Nekhen has given thee.” [Mercer, 1952]

“Utterance 1294. He has given to thee his spirits, the jackals, like (to) Horus who is in his house, like (to) Ḥnti (Osiris) chief of the mighty. A durable offering is made for thee. Utterance 1295. Anubis, chief of the sḥ-ntr, has commanded that thou come in as a star, as god of the morning (or, as god of the morning star), that thou pass through the region of Horus of the South and that thou pass through the region of Horus of the North. Utterance 1296. (And) men will construct with their arms a stairway to thy throne. He comes to thee his father; he comes to thee Geb. Utterance 1297. Do for him that which thou hast done for his brother, Osiris, on this day of thy feast, the water being full (i. e. at inundation), when (his) bones are counted, when (his) sandals are repaired, when his nails, upper and lower, are cleaned for him. There will come to him (people of) the Upper Egyptian 'itr.t-palace and of the northern 'itr.t-palace, bowing ...” [Mercer, 1952]

“RECITATION. You have your water, you have your inundation, you have your outflow that came from Osiris. The sky's door has been opened to you, Nut's door has been pulled open to you. The sky's door has been opened to you, the Cool Waters' door has been pulled open to you. “Endure!” says Isis, “In peace!” says Nephthys, when they have seen their brother. Raise yourself! Your bonds have been untied for you, your dust has been cleared away for you. So, you shall sit on your metal chair, clean from your four jars and your four water-jars that have come from the god's palace for you so that you might become cleansed with natron-water, that have been filled to the brim for you from the natron canal, that Horus of Nekhen has given you when he gave you his jackal akhs as Horus in his house, as the foremost one at the fore of the controlling powers” [Mercer, 1952]

“How permanent is that which has been done for you! Anubis, foremost of the god's booth, has commanded that you descend as a star, as the morning god. You shall wander southern Horus's mounds, you shall wander northern Horus's mounds, and those of estimation will lay down their arms for the stairway to your seat. He has come to you, his father; he has

come to you, Geb. Do for him that which you did for his brother Osiris on the day of catching you complete from the water, 132 of allotting bones and fastening sandals. Make his fingernails and toenails faultless [for] him, so that the Nile-Valley shrine and the Delta shrine might come to him in obeisance [...].” [Mercer, 1952]

Charlemagne

Could we imagine a dead king on a throne in a secret vault? Well, let us remember Charlemagne, because of a story about a hidden chamber in Aachen Cathedral. The king died January 28, 814. “He was buried that same day”, in the Cathedral, “although the cold weather and the nature of his illness made such a hurried burial unnecessary. ... A later story, told by Otho of Lomello, Count of the Palace at Aachen in the time of Emperor Otto III, would claim that he and Otto had discovered Charlemagne's tomb: Charlemagne, they claimed, was seated upon a throne, wearing a crown and holding a sceptre, his flesh almost entirely incorrupt. In 1165, Emperor Frederick I re-opened the tomb again and placed the emperor in a sarcophagus beneath the floor of the cathedral”. <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Charlemagne>

It seems that it was not a throne but a curule seat, that is a usually foldable and transportable chair, noted for its uses in Ancient Rome. It was a symbol of political or military power.

Fig. 4 - Octavian, togate, seated on curule chair.

“In the gallery of the Basilica he [Charlemagne] had erected his marble throne, covered with plates of gold, studded with Greek cameos and astral gems from Nineveh or Babylon. Before the throne were the stairs, straight down descending to the sepulcher which Charlemagne had already dug deep for himself in the holy ground, even when he raised that marble throne. Soon afterwards the huge broad flagstone which covers the vault was heaved up, - there they reverently deposited the embalmed corpse, surrounded by ghastly magnificence, sitting erect on his curule chair, clad in his silken robes, ponderous with broidery, pearls, and orfray, the imperial diadem on his head, his closed eyelids covered, his face swathed in the dead clothes, girt with his baldric, the ivory horn slung in his scarf, his good sword Joyeuse by his side, the Gospel-book open on his lap, - musk and amber, and sweet spices poured around, - his golden shield and golden sceptre pendant before

him” [Palgrave, 1851].

The body

The article “Egypt experts set sights on finding lost Pharaoh's remains in Great Pyramid” [Hoare, 2019] tells that “EGYPT experts, including world-renowned archaeologist Dr Zahi Hawass, believe Pharaoh Khufu’s body can finally be found in a huge void discovered inside the Great Pyramid of Giza, Express.co.uk can reveal.” In the article we can find again that Dr Zahi Hawass considers that the Great Pyramid has 'lots of voids’.

“Until recently, many Egyptologists had believed his plan had failed, due to the discovery of an empty sarcophagus believed to have contained his body. However, that all changed in 2017, after a group of French archaeologists discovered a void near the Queen's Chamber during the ScanPyramid project. Less than two years later, in August 2019, it was revealed a huge second chamber had also been found, this time to the right of the King’s Chamber and it is safe to say Egyptologists are excited about the discoveries to come”. Dr Zahi Hawass tells that “We asked them to give us more specific data about this void so we can know more about what this space was used for.”

“Dr Hawass continued, expressing a belief that the body of Khufu could actually be hiding in this void. He added: “If you know how the Great Pyramid was constructed, then you know it has lots of voids.”. “We hope to find the body of Khufu could be discovered, that something important could be discovered in these voids”.

Fig. 5 - KHUFU – Courtesy Osiritkos for Wikimedia.

The Pindar's iron throne

We are not surprised to imagine a king or a god in throne, but in ancient Greece we can find a poet sitting on a throne, an iron throne.

“The states of Greece paid him honors that were almost divine: they admitted him to share with the gods in their gifts and oblations; and the Oracle of Delphos commanded the people to present to Pindar a proportion of their first-fruits. In the temple of Apollo, at Delphos, there was an *iron throne of Pindar*, on which he sat whenever he visited that city, and recited the verses he had composed in honour of Apollo. This throne was preserved a long time after his death.” [Francis Lee, 1816].

Fig. 6 - A cut, polished and etched face of Toluca iron meteorite, displaying Widmanstätten Pattern. Image Courtesy H. Raab for Wikipedia

During the Early Iron Age

Here an excerpt from [Cesnola, 1914].

“Iron was known in Egypt as a great rarity from the earliest dynasties, but did not supersede bronze for common use until the XXVI, after 664 BC. Tribute of iron was, however, brought to Egypt from North Syria under the XIX Dynasty (1350-1200 B.C.) and the Biblical description of Jabin, King of Hazor, with his "four hundred chariots of iron" probably represents the state of things there in the Early Iron Age. The famous iron-work of Damascus very likely had its origin in this period. On the other hand, the Greeks ascribed an early iron- working industry to a people whom they called Chalybes in Northeastern Asia Minor; and after the eighth century both they and the Phoenicians of Tyre obtained iron from this district. Thirdly, in the Homeric Age, which represents a period of transition, iron was being exported oversea from the Taphian country in the northwest of Greece; other Greek traditions point to Chalcis in Euboea, and to the West

of Crete, as early centres of iron trade; so that there is some reason to believe that very early Mediterranean iron workings lay in this direction. Probably when once the discovery was made, how to produce iron on a commercial scale, iron-works sprang up almost simultaneously in many separate regions. In Cyprus itself, iron was worked on a considerable scale round Tamassos and also round Soloi on the northwest coast, from an early period of the Iron Age. Iron was indeed known in the island, as in most parts of the Minoan world, for a short period before this was regarded as a precious metal, and used only for rings, sceptres, and fine inlaid work. Its magnetic properties, and the rapidity with which it decays, probably caused it to be regarded in Cyprus, as elsewhere, as something uncanny, and potent for good or harm: a belief which survived in modern superstitions about blacksmiths, and the "luck" of old horseshoes. Even after iron had come into common use, and into exclusive use for a few specialized types of implements and weapons, bronze was not wholly displaced in Cyprus, even for weapons; spears, in particular, are found in bronze associated with swords and knives of iron. For defensive armour and the arrow, bronze was still preferred all through the Hellenic and Graeco-Roman ages". (Link to the "Handbook of the Cesnola collection of antiquities from Cyprus").

From the Guide of British Museum (1904)

Let us return to the Egyptian antiquities.

From "A Guide to the First and Second Egyptian Rooms Predynastic Antiquities, Mummies, Mummy-cases, and Other Objects Connected with the Funeral Rites of the Ancient ", British Museum, Department of Egyptian and Assyrian Antiquities, written by Sir Ernest Alfred Wallis Budge, 1904. "The earlier predynastic antiquities belong to the Neolithic age, when men in Egypt had no knowledge of the use of metal. In the latter part of the predynastic period copper was introduced, and was used side by side with stone. The antiquities of the later predynastic and the earlier archaic periods belong then to the stage of human civilization which is commonly known as Aeneolithic, or Chalcolithic, Under the IVth dynasty, i.e. at the end of the Archaic Period, we find the first traces of the use of Bronze in Egypt, and henceforward the Egyptians remained users of bronze, though, since Iron was always well known to them, it is impossible to speak of a definite Bronze Age in Egypt.

It is certain that iron was known to the Egyptians from the earliest times, for the oldest religious texts extant, which date from about BC 3500, and were copied from far older archetypes, speak of the heavens being formed of a plate of iron, and the Deity is said to sit upon a throne of iron, the sides of which are ornamented with the faces of lions, and have four legs, the feet of which are in the form of hoofs of bulls.

The Egyptian word for "iron" $B\dot{A}A$, or $B\dot{A}AENPET$ i.e. " $B\dot{A}A$ of heaven," is of course meteoric iron, and this phrase is the exact equivalent of the old Sumerian ideographic group

→→† † AN . BAR, "iron."

The Coptic word for "iron," BENIPE, which is a direct descendant of $B\dot{A}AENPET$, conclusively proves that this expression means "iron," and iron only. But, in order to avoid the conclusion that iron was known to the Egyptians at this early period, it has been supposed that $B\dot{A}A$ meant "crystal" ; this, however, is disproved by the fact that representations of weapons, knives, tools, etc., which are of a blue colour, are found upon the monuments of all periods, and, as it is clear that they cannot have been made of crystal, they must be iron". The Guide is also telling that the "oldest specimen of iron from Egypt was found in one of the air passages of the Pyramid of Cheops (B.C. 3700), and may be seen in the Second Egyptian Room (Table-case K, No. 29)."

The metal throne

Previously, we have seen that "iron" was the word used to translate the Pyramid Texts. However, we can find also used the term "metal". For instance, in [Spence, 1917]: "Sit on your metal throne. Receive your mace and your ames-staff and guide those-who-are-in-Nu, give orders to the gods and establish the akh as his akh. Follow your course and row your watercourse like Ra on the shores of the sky. O Pepi/O my father, raise yourself! Go as your akh! (PT spell)". And, in [Jurewicz et al., 2020], and in [Allen, 2007]. "You shall sit on a metal throne; with your face that of the great god; Make for yourself your place at the fore of the west, make for yourself your control at the fore of the gods. Watch over those [you] love, and they [will make] your festivals". "You sit on your metal throne and render judgment with the Dual Ennead. Ho, Neith! You have received your head, you have your teeth, you have your hair. You open the doors that bar people, stable for the course of eternity. Ho, Neith!"

In [Spence, 1917], we can find again a metal throne. When talking about the The Egyptian Heaven, [Spence, 1917] tells that its exact position "does not appear to have been located". "In heaven dwelt the great god Ra, who sat upon a metal throne , the sides of which were embossed with the faces of lions and the hoofs of bulls".

Were the Egyptians of the Old Kingdom distinguishing copper from iron, or used the same word "metal" for both of them?

Fig. 7- Left: Head of a Lion, Egypt. Courtesy Metropolitan Museum of Art - Creative Commons CC0 1.0 Universal Public Domain Dedication - <https://picryl.com/media/head-of-a-lion-d3069b>
– Right: Chair from tomb of Tutankhamun, reproduction in the Fitchburg Art Museum, Fitchburg, Massachusetts, USA. This artwork is old enough so that it is in the public domain. Photography was permitted in the museum without restriction. 14 June 2013, Work Courtesy Daderot for Wikipedia

About the iron plate in the air passage of Khufu's pyramid, and mentioned above, we have more details in "The Iron Plate in the Great Pyramid", by Larry Orcutt, in Catchpenny Mysteries, 2000. <http://www.catchpenny.org/iron.html> and <https://archive.is/Mwy8f>

"It would seem, then, that the iron plate found by J.R. Hill in 1837 is not contemporary with the construction of the pyramid, but rather dates to the post-medieval (Islamic) period sometime between the 16th and 18th centuries. It would be a matter for speculation just how such a plate might have found its way down a joint between the pyramid stones, but after the Arab conquest there was much activity at the Giza pyramids. Hill's report that the iron "was taken out by me from an inner joint, after having removed by blasting the two outer tiers of the stones" and "that no joint or opening of any sort was connected with the above-mentioned joint" was made ex post facto, and one may well wonder how closely he examined the joints before blasting considering he had no idea that he might find something there".

Horus

The Pyramid Texts describe also the nature of the pharaoh in different characters as both

Horus and Osiris. In [Budge, 1988], we can find him as a star, and also the same details, about the throne, that we have read in the previous section.

“He is the brother of the Moon, and the son of SOTHIS (SIRIUS); he revolves in heaven like ORION; and he rises in his place like a star, being one of the everlasting and never-setting stars of the northern sky. He is more resplendent than the AKHU, more perfect than the perfect ones, more stable than the stable gods, and he sits on the shoulders of RA. HORUS exchanges his Ka with him. ... He is arrayed in white apparel which is like unto the finest raiment of those who sit on the throne of living right and truth, and the framework of his iron throne is decorated with the faces of lions, and its legs have the feet of bull. On his head he wears the great Urerit Crown”.

Glittering in the nightly sky

The opening of the mouth ceremony, that we have mentioned before, was an ancient Egyptian ritual described in funerary texts such as the Pyramid Texts. A specific instrument was used for this ritual.

In www.ucl.ac.uk/museums-static/digitalegypt/religion , 2003, by University College London, in the translation of an episode in the tomb-chapel of Rekhmira, we can read “I open your mouth for you with the nua-blade, I have opened your mouth for you with the nua-blade, the meskhetyu-blade of iron, that opens the mouths of the gods”.

In [Wainwright, 1932], it is told that the adze used in the ritual, was the earthly representative of the original heavenly adze, made of *mshtyw* of *bi3* which opened the mouth of the gods, with which Horus opened the mouth of his father, Osiris.

That heavenly original glitters nightly in the skies
our constellation of the Great Bear. The other form it adopts is , the Foreleg of
the Bull³, and that was equally efficacious, either as a little iron instrument or as the leg itself cut off the sacrificial bull.

And the stars are made of iron, and pieces of them, sometimes, are falling down.

“In the Pyramid Texts, the imperishable stars are paralleled with the king’s iron bones, as if to suggest that they were made of iron ... The fact that the northern circumpolar stars were represented by two adzes of iron provides support for this interpretation” [Alford, 2004]. Alford is also telling that in the Coffin Texts, it is written that “the deceased swallows magic in the form of ‘iron of a star’ (*bjā n sbat*), which strongly suggests that stars were made of iron”, meteoric iron.

See also <http://www.joanannlansberry.com/fotoart/met-muzm/adze-mdl.html>

The Bull's Leg

In the article entitled “Ancient Egyptian temple reveals previously unknown star constellations”, written by Laura Geggel, November 19, 2020, Live Science , we can find an “ancient Egyptian depiction of the Big Dipper, seen here in the shape of a bull's leg. It includes seven stars and is tied to a stake by a goddess in hippo form (right). The Big Dipper is considered the manifestation of the evil god Seth, who murdered his brother Osiris. The goddess prevents Seth from reaching Osiris in the underworld — a myth made possible because the constellation never dips below the horizon”. During the restoration of the Temple of Esna, researchers cleaned ancient scenes representing constellations, “including the Big Dipper (known as Mesekhtiu) and Orion (known as Sah). They also found inscriptions about previously unknown constellations, including one called "Apedu n Ra," or "the geese of Ra," who is the ancient Egyptian sun deity, Leitz said. However, without an image to accompany these descriptions, there's no way to know which stars in the night sky they describe, he said”.

The metal of Seth

“Ownership of the adze is credited to Wepwawet, while the iron itself is said to have issued from Seth. What does this tell us? As regards Seth, it is likely that the text refers to the meteoritic iron of which the adze was made; since the adze was modeled on the northern stars and since Seth was held to dwell in those stars, the iron adze would have been viewed as the metal of Seth” [Alford, 2004].

However, Alan Alford continues remarking the role of Wepwawet, the jackal-god. He tells that the original form of the god was a wolf. The name of the god means literally “ ‘the opener of the ways’ (Wp-wawt), but he is also called ‘the opener of the body’.

In the Pyramid Texts, he is said to be on high in the sky, and he opens the ways for the ascent of the king.” [Alford, 2004].

Fig. 8 - Image Courtesy kairoinfo4u - “Abydos, Temple of Sety I - Second Hypostyle Hall, Western Wall second limestone pier between the entrances of the Chapels of Ptah and Ra-Horakhty - The jackal-headed God Wepwawet, also called Upuaut embraces King Sety. As lord of the cemetery at Abydos Wepwawet was being seen as one who opened the ways to and protects the deceased through the Underworld”.

‘Opening of the Mouth and Eyes’ ritual

At the link digitalegypt.ucl.ac.uk, University College London, we can find a detailed description of the ritual. Let us report some sentences.

“The '*Opening of the Mouth and Eyes*' (generally abbreviated to 'Opening of the Mouth') is the ancient Egyptian title of a ritual attested from the Old Kingdom to the Roman Period. In essence it might be described as a *consecration ritual for images in human form*. It is known to have been performed on statues and, from the New Kingdom (about 1550-1069 BC) at least, coffins”. The site tells that “specially designated persons used special ritual tools to touch the mouth and eyes of the image to enable a spirit to receive food and drink, to breathe, and to see. Sustenance and light are the two key aspects of life desired for the person for eternity”. It is also told “the ritual illustrates a concept of sculpture as birth. This concept also finds expression in the Egyptian language, in its vocabulary for sculpture: the fashioning of the image is 'giving birth', the sculptor is 'the one who causes to live'.”

Among the tools for the ritual, the web site is mentioning a forked blade, named peseshkaf, a word interpreted “in later periods as 'splitter of his ka-spirit' “, the serpent blade, named werhekau which means 'Great of Power', and the adze-shaped blades, named meskhetyu and nua.

Sources about the ritual range from Old Kingdom to Roman Period. E. Otto [Otto, 1960] collected them and proposed the following episodes: Episodes 1-9: preliminary rites - Episodes 10-22: animation of the statue - Episodes 23-42: meat offerings aligned with Upper Egypt - Episodes 43-46: meat offerings aligned with Lower Egypt - Episodes 47-71: funerary meal - Episodes 72-75: closing rites.

The second Khufu solar boat

Near Akhet Khufu, that is the pyramid, some metal was found.

“A piece of wood recovered at a dig near the Great Pyramid of Giza shows for the first time that ancient Egyptians used metal in their boats, archaeologists said Wednesday [in 2016]. Circular and U-shaped metal hooks were found in one of the components of a boat, discovered the same year as Khufu's "solar boat", buried near the Great Pyramid. Solar boats, buried in pits next to royal burial chambers, may have been used for a pharaoh's funeral procession, while others were intended for travels in the afterworld”.
<https://phys.org/news/2016-08-ancient-egyptians-metal-wooden-ships.html>

And also “Last week, the team raised a beam from the eighth layer that is eight meters long, 40 centimeters wide and four centimeters thick. It was taken to the laboratory built on the Giza Plateau for the Khufu Second Boat Project for it to be dried and stabilized. Upon closer examination, the beam was found to have unique features: a number of U

and L-shaped metal hooks embedded in the surface of the wood. There are no such metal elements in any of the beams from Khufu's first solar boat. Archaeologists believe the metal parts may have been the ancient version of oar locks. ... The U-shaped hooks were used "to place the paddles to prevent friction of wood against wood", said Sakuji Yoshimura, an Egyptologist from Japan". <http://www.thehistoryblog.com/archives/43967>

Was the metal copper? Or iron, meteoric iron?

Fig. 9 - The Kamil crater in ACME Mapper. The crater has been created by an iron meteorite.

Black-market and Kamil Crater

In any case, where we can find iron or meteoric iron in Egypt? For meteoric iron, a site – the Gebel Kamil Crater - was recently discovered and looted. In [Broad, 2011], The New York Times remembers that a black-market, that is, an illegal market of meteoric fragments exists. "The discovery of a rich and historically significant meteorite crater in southern Egypt, just north of the Sudanese border, has shown the voracious appetite for new fragments. Just as scientists appeared to be on the cusp of decrypting the evidence to solve an ancient puzzle, looters plundered the desolate site". As previously told, the site is that of the Kamil Crater [Folco et al., 2010].

"The mystery began thousands of years ago with Egyptian hieroglyphs, which refer to the "iron of heaven." Archaeologists have long debated whether the Egyptians made artifacts from iron meteorites that fell to Earth in fiery upheavals. The main evidence came from ancient knife blades of iron that had high concentrations of nickel — a rare element in the Earth's crust that was considered a signature of extraterrestrial origin. But doubts grew as investigators found terrestrial sites rich in nickel that ancient peoples could have mined. And scientists in Egypt never found an impact crater and a nearby lode of meteorites" [Broad, 2011]. But in June 2008, Vincenzo de Michele, Italian mineralogist and explorer, by means of Google Earth, discovered a crater. With Mario Di Martino, Italian National

Institute for Astrophysics, Torino, formed an expedition that surveyed the site in February 2009. “To their delight, the desolate area bristled with iron meteorites — more than 5,000 of them — and they named the crater Gebel Kamil, after a nearby mountain” [Broad, 2011].

Article [Broad, 2011] tells that the team members put a bottle with a signed note inside at the crater’s bottom. “A return expedition in February 2010, found that the bottle had disappeared. The secret was out. A few months later, in June, meteorites from the crater were for sale at a show in Ensisheim, France” [Broad, 2011].

The Kamil crater is estimated to be less than 5,000 years old [Folco et al., 2010] and shows a well-preserved rayed structure. The crater is quite recent then, however it is in the time range for being considered for a comparison of its iron with the iron of Tutankhamun's dagger. In [Comelli et al., 2016], the iron of Kamil crater had been included. “In order to investigate if known iron meteorites within the ancient Egyptian trade sphere could be linked to the studied blade, [the authors] sorted all the known iron meteorites found in the region from the MetBase [Meteorite Information Database]. Within an area 2000 km in radius arbitrarily centered in the Red Sea, Egypt (i.e., extending from central-eastern Sahara to the Arabic Peninsula, Mesopotamia, Iran, and Eastern Mediterranean area), 20 iron meteorite finds are present in the database. *Only one, group IVA, the fine octahedrite, named Kharga* (Egypt, 31°07'57"N, 25°02'50"E, found 2000, May 8, 1 kg; Grossman and Zipfel 2001), has Ni and Co contents (11.77 wt% and 0.437 wt%, respectively) within 10% of the composition of the studied blade” [Comelli et al., 2016].

“Kharga meteorite - The meteorite, now called Kharga, was found in 2000, and contains a mixture of iron with 10.8 percent nickel and 0.58 percent cobalt — *the same composition as the dagger*. None of the ten other meteorites found in or near Egypt matched that particular composition.” In “King Tut’s Meteorite Dagger: It Came From Outer Space”, written by Rick Robinson, 2020, link <https://now.northropgrumman.com>

“*Common iron meteorite prices are generally in the range of US\$0.50 to US\$5.00 per gram. Stone meteorites are much scarcer and priced in the US\$2.00 to US\$20.00 per gram range for the more common material. It is not unusual for the truly scarce material to exceed US\$1,000 per gram*”. <http://www.meteorlab.com> And we can find “*Gebel Kamil Iron Meteorites For Sale*” - Find / Fall: Find – 2009 - Location: Al Wadi al Jadid, Egypt - Total Known Weight: 1.6 Metric Tons. About \$2 million.

Other non destructive analyses

In [CNRS.FR], we find told that the “Iron Age began in Anatolia and the Caucasus around 1200 BCE. But nearly 2,000 years earlier, various cultures were already fashioning objects out of iron. These items were extremely rare and always greatly treasured. Iron

ore abounds on the Earth's surface. So what made these artifacts so valuable? Initial research had shown that some were made with iron from meteorites, which led scientists to wonder how many others were. Albert Jambon (2017) gathered the available data and conducted his own nondestructive chemical analyses of samples using a portable X-ray fluorescence spectrometer". Jambon studied iron artifacts including beads from Gerzeh, Egypt, 3200 BC, a dagger from Alaca Höyük in Turkey, 2500 BC, a pendant from Umm el-Marra in Syria, 2300 BCE, an axe from Ugarit, in Syria too, 1400 BC, and *several others from the Shang dynasty civilization*, China, 1400 BC. He studied also the dagger, bracelet, and headrest of Tutankhamun. Not only the dagger, analyses have also shown that Tutankhamun's bracelet and headrest "were made from the iron of at least two different meteorites, suggesting that an active search was carried out for valuable iron meteorites in ancient times, he said" [SCI-A].

A gift from Mitanni?

Before discussing the beads of the necklace from Gerzeh, let us consider recent news about Tutankhamun's meteoric iron dagger, according the results obtained by a Japan-based research team, as reported by [Archaeology.wiki, 2022].

"Tutankhamun's iron dagger ... reached Egypt as an import from the ancient Empire of Mitanni, according to researchers from Japan's Chiba Institute of Technology (CIT), who published an article in the journal *Meteoritics & Planetary Science*." The article is [Matsui et al. 2022]. "In February 2020, CIT researchers reached the Egyptian Museum in Cairo to obtain new results concerning the dagger's material and craftsmanship. According to their published research paper, they conducted nondestructive and noncontact chemical analyses of the meteoritic dagger blade at the Museum. For comparison, they analyzed the Shirahagi iron meteorite, the source of the Japanese historical sword Ryuseito which is housed in Toyama Science Museum; analysis in Toyama took place in the same way and using the same analytical instrument and techniques as in Cairo". The researchers conformed the "iron meteorite (octahedrite) as the source of the dagger's iron". They also noted some features of the dagger's gold handle, or hilt, which is also decorated with semi-precious stones and granulation. "The hilt's ornaments had been attached with quicklime, a material which did not reach Egypt before the Ptolemaic period, instead of gypsum, the material normally used in Pharaonic times. All these elements show that the dagger might have been manufactured outside of Egypt, but where exactly?"

The article Archaeology.wiki, 2022, continues explaining that the populations of Anatolia knew how to forge iron from meteorites already from at least around 2300 BC. This date is that of the oldest meteoric iron dagger excavated at Alacahöyük, Turkey. "Anatolia's southeast end formed part of the Empire of Mitanni". This empire had diplomatic relations with Egypt of the 18th Dynasty. This relationship is well-documented by 14

letters of the “Amarna Letters, the diplomatic correspondence archive found in the Palace of Tell el Amarna, where Tutankhamun’s reign probably started”. Archaeology.wiki, 2022, tells that “two of these letters (designated EA 22 and EA 23), both sent from the Mitannian King Tushratta to Tutankhamun’s grandfather, Amenhotep III, contain the description of iron-blade daggers with elements of gold and precious materials”.

In [Matsui et al. 2022], the authors tells that the “evidence for iron in the Amarna letters can be found almost exclusively in a list of gifts sent to Amenhotep III (1417–1379 B.C.) of Egypt by Tusratta, the king of Mitanni, ... when he married the princess Taduhepa to Amenhotep III (Lucas & Harris, 2012; McNutt, 1990; Morkot, 2010; Rainey, 2014). In this document, habakin(n)u (ha-bal-ki-i-in-nu) is translated as “iron” (Moran, 1992). According to the translation by W. L. Moran, on VS XII 199 = EA 22 I, 32–35 (p. 51 of Moran, 1992), a dagger is described: “1 dagger, the blade of which is of iron, its guard, of gold, with designs; its haft of ebony with calf figurines; overlaid with gold; its pommel is of ... -stone; its (...) ..., overlaid with gold, with designs, 6 shekels (= ca. 50 g) gold have been used on it.”. A similar description can be found in VS XII 199 = EA 22 III, 7–9 (p. 54 of Moran, 1992): “1 dagger, the blade, of iron; its guard, of gold, with designs; its hilt, of ...; an inlay of genuine lapis lazuli; its pommel, of hiliba-stone. 5 shekels (= ca. 42 g) gold have been used on it.”

Archaeology.wiki stresses that the blades described in the Letters do not fit with Tutankhamun’s dagger. However, the Mitannian King had access to “two iron daggers, in an era where iron was a rare material, and Anatolia was part of Mitanni at the time of Amenhotep III and Tushratta”. Due to these facts, the research team suggested that the Tutankhamun’s iron dagger was a gift from the king of Mitanni to Amenhotep III. “At that time in Egypt, iron was considered an element that fell from the sky on rare occasions and was about 80 times more valuable than gold. Tutankhamun probably inherited his grandfather’s iron dagger and it was placed in his tomb when he died at a young age”, according to Takafumi Matsui, president of the Chiba Institute of Technology.

Archaeology.wiki, 2022, notes that “the theory of the CIT team has already started to receive criticism. In her personal blog, archaeologist Andrea Sinclair, an expert on hybrid iconography and interconnections in Tutankhamun’s era, states that “most of the archaeologically related claims from this paper are either hyperbole, incorrect or based on out of date theories”, as, while “the chemical analyses employed by the authors were professional and thorough, however the conclusions drawn from this data are flawed and ignore the broader historical and archaeological context”. As Sinclair observes, Mitanni was not in Anatolia, meteoric iron sources have been documented in Egypt’s Kharga Oasis, and extensive and multifold contacts between states in the Late Bronze Age allowed for a broad reach of technologies, so that it is impossible to claim a particular place of origin for the dagger. Also, this dagger is a variation of a recorded Egyptian type, while it is highly unlikely that a Pharaoh would have been buried with a foreign gift. It is

thus impossible to associate Tutanhamun's iron dagger with Mitanni; at least for the time being." [Archaeology.wiki, 2022, Sinclair, 2022].

Kharga Oasis origin

"So what are their claims?" [Sinclair, 2022].

"...it has been known for years that the iron of this dagger is not of terrestrial origin." [Matsui et al., 2022].

"Yes, it has, the iron blade was published by Bjorkman in 1973, in 'Meteors and Meteorites in the Ancient Near East', but to be clear, the dagger blade was not unique to this tomb as there were at least 18 other meteoric iron objects in the assemblage, consisting of a model headrest, a wedjat eye and 16 model chisels, these are pretty standard objects for an Egyptian burial, they are just made of meteoric iron instead of copper or bronze. See also Broschat et al 2017, Himmlisch: Die Eisenobjekte aus dem Grabe des Tutanchamun (for scientific examination of the iron objects from this tomb)." [Sinclair, 2022].

"...Its extraterrestrial origin has again been confirmed by a Japanese research team from the Chiba Institute of Technology. ... It is therefore confirmed that the metal of the dagger is made essentially of iron with between 10 and 12% nickel, which is not found in terrestrial iron ore in these proportions but in octahedrites, famous iron meteorites. We also find iron sulphide characteristic of these meteorites but above all the famous structure known as Widmanstätten, with patterns indicating an alternation of different iron-nickel alloys and which it is impossible to obtain on Earth, in any case in ordinary metallurgical processes. In fact, the discovery of a so-called Widmanstätten structure is considered proof that we are in the presence of a meteorite". [Matsui et al., 2022].

"Again, we knew the blade was meteoric iron, not 'extraterrestrial' per se, a problematic (and hyperbolic) use which infers to the reader that the exploiters of the mineral saw it fall as a meteor and collected the debris 'because that was significant'. This is highly unlikely, it was much more likely to be a mineral found in certain areas and used because of its appearance. The source of the iron of this dagger was established on the basis of nickel content as the Kharga Oasis region in the Egyptian Western Desert in Comelli et al 2016, The Meteoric Origin of Tutankhamen's Iron Dagger Blade." [Sinclair, 2022].

The necklace from Gerzeh

The beads from Gerzeh were used for a necklace. An article by Sci News (2013), www.sci-news.com/archaeology, explains that the ancient Egyptian iron beads were discovered in 1911. A study demonstrated that the beads "were hammered from pieces of meteorites, rather than iron ore. Carefully hammered into thin sheets before being rolled

into tubes, the nine beads were originally strung into a necklace together with other exotic minerals such as gold and gemstones, revealing the high value of this exotic material in ancient times. “The shape of the beads was obtained by smithing and rolling, most likely involving multiple cycles of hammering, and not by the traditional stone-working techniques such as carving or drilling which were used for the other beads found in the same tomb,” explained Prof Thilo Rehren from the Hamad bin Khalifa University in Qatar, who is a lead author of the paper published in the *Journal of Archaeological Science* . The article is given in Ref. [Rehren et al., 2013].

“The Gerzeh culture, also called Naqada II, refers to the archaeological stage at Gerzeh (also Girza or Jirzah), a prehistoric Egyptian cemetery located along the west bank of the Nile. ... Gerzeh is situated only several miles due east of the oasis of Faiyum. The Gerzeh culture is a material culture identified by archaeologists. It is the second of three phases of the prehistoric Naqada cultures and so is also known as Naqada II. The Gerzeh culture was preceded by the Amratian culture ("Naqada I") and followed by the Naqada III ("protodynastic" or "Semainian culture").” The Gerzeh culture dates circa 3,650 BC — circa 3,300 BC.

Origin of the words

It is time to add some sentences from [Johnson et al. 2013].

“Within the near east, we find text references to iron and meteorites, but the exact origins of the words used for iron within the region are complex and despite many previous studies remain largely unproven. ... Complex linguistic issues regarding difference in the reading of ancient Egyptian terms for copper and iron caused massive confusion in early translations”. In [Johnson et al. 2013] it is told that “some linguists made no acknowledgment of the difference”. And also “The term *biA* eventually translated to mean iron; these early references to iron typically describe objects or aspects of the sky and so have a relatively broad meaning. As Egyptians at this time would not have understood the intricacy of iron metal chemistry, such early terms possibly reflected other iron-related materials, such as haematite or any material that had a visual resemblance to fresh or weathered iron”. However – it is stressed in [Johnson et al. 2013] - “from the late 18th Dynasty, approximately 1300 BCE, the term *biA-n-pt* starts to be used, which literally reads **iron from the sky** and from this point onwards, it is applied to describe all types of iron (Bjorkman, 1973), the term becoming synonymous with metallic iron in general”.

The authors of [Johnson et al. 2013] note that reasons for the creation of this new word at this particular point in time are unknown. They mention that the term – possibly - was coming from “a literal description resulting from the observance of a major event by the Egyptian population”, that required the creation of a new term. “The witnessing of a localized event would probably not be sufficient to influence the Egyptian literate

minority (scribes) to make and use a new word so dominantly, whereas a larger event, such as a shower of meteorites or large impact event would leave little doubt to where the iron had originated and would be witnessed by many”. Then the Gebel Kamil crater in southern Egypt is mentioned in [Johnson et al. 2013]. “The unpredictable nature of such an event may have been sufficient to require a new descriptor, and sufficiently significant for the term “iron from the sky” subsequently to be used indiscriminately for all metallic iron” [Johnson et al. 2013]. At the time of Tutankhamun, it seems that “iron” was the “iron from sky”. Or “metal from sky”?

Stone and Fire

There is also a remarkable link that it is necessary to stress, and it is that of meteorites and fire. We can find it in [Graves-Brown, 2010]. “Although the Egyptians used the fire-drill, which is attested archaeologically and iconographically (Newberry et al. 1896, 23, fig. 68, p. 5; Stocks 2003, 52–55), the ability of flint to produce sparks, particularly when struck with meteoric iron, must have been familiar. While no strike-a-lights have been found, they may have gone unrecognised. ... Alternatively, the Egyptians may have preferred the fire-drill. Fire is more difficult to produce from flint and naturally occurring iron than from a fire-drill (Runnels 1994)”. And also “Connection between flint and fire could be mediated through third parties, for example, Seth, snakes or meteoric iron”.

“Within the realm of the stellar and flint, there appears to be a constellation of ideas surrounding the northern night sky, meteoric iron, Seth and Osiris. With the exception of Wainwright’s (1932a and b) observations on the connection between Seth, meteoric iron and flint, these entities do not seem to have been previously discussed as a group”. In [Graves-Brown, 2010], we find discussed “connection between flint and the moon” and “between flint and the “opening of the mouth” ceremony”. “Several of the implements used in this ceremony, particularly the adze, foreleg of an ox and the ntrwj-blades are stellar (Roth 1993). The adze and foreleg particularly relate to the northern sky”. [Roth, 1993] discussed the ntrwj-blades and fingers of bja. “A significant peculiarity of the ntrwj is their composition. They are said in all the textual sources to be of bja, which was clearly a material thought to be meteoritic”.

Benben and Bennu, the Phoenix

After talking of the beads of Gerzeh, in “[The meteoric origins of Egypt’s first ironwork](#)”, guest blogger Isadora Fontaine tells that “Interestingly, this is not the only meteorite-related story to come out of Egypt... The mysterious Benben stone, a cult object which once stood in the solar temple at Heliopolis, may have been a meteorite that had a conical or pyramidal shape. We will never know for sure what the Benben really was, since the stone was lost in antiquity, but some suggest that its shape may have been the inspiration

for the tips of obelisks and even the pyramids themselves”.

“In the creation myth of the Heliopolitan form of ancient Egyptian religion, Benben was the mound that arose from the primordial waters Nu upon which the creator deity Atum settled. The Benben stone (also known as a pyramidion) is the top stone of the pyramid. It is also related to the obelisk” [Wikipedia](#). “In the Pyramid Texts, e.g. Utterances 587 and 600, Atum himself is at times referred to as "mound". It was said to have turned into a small pyramid, located in Heliopolis ... within which Atum was said to dwell. Other cities developed their own myths of the primeval mound. ... The Benben stone, named after the mound, was a sacred stone in the temple of Ra at Heliopolis. It was the location on which the first rays of the sun fell. It is thought to have been the prototype for later obelisks and the capstones of the great pyramids were based on its design. ... The bird deity Bennu, which was probably the inspiration for the phoenix, was venerated at Heliopolis, where it was said to be living on the Benben stone or on the holy willow tree. According to Barry Kemp, the connection between the benben, the phoenix, and the sun may well have been based on alliteration: the rising, weben, of the sun sending its rays towards the benben, on which the bennu bird lives. Utterance 600, § 1652 of the Pyramid Texts speaks of Atum as you rose up, as the benben, in the Mansion of the Bennu in Heliopolis.” from Wikipedia again.

Meteoric Iron?

Daniel E. Mitchell writes in his “Finding Your Benben Stone And Building Your Great Pyramid of Success” [Mitchell, 2014], the following. “Theorists have speculated that the Benben Stone may have been formed out of a meteoric iron which tied the ancient Egyptians with a fervent devotion of the stars. The most existent writing that referenced the Benben Stone was found in the Book of Coming Forth by Day (The Book of the Dead). Bushby imparts that it was called the “Throne of Radiance”. This meteor type of conical object appears to have been described in the Fifth Hour of the Duat Underworld of the Coffin texts, as having a bell formation to it, and possessing a fiery presence. As a probable meteoric object, the Benben Stone is believed to have glorified the base of the Mansion of the Benben located at the temple structure associated with Atum-Ra at Anu / Iunu / On / Heliopolis, and may have influenced the veneration of other meteoric stones that have surfaced at Egyptian temples associated with the god Amon / Amun.”

Iron or Copper?

In [Burke, 1991], we find the following. “In 1911, Wainwright discovered nine iron beads in two predynastic graves at Gerzeh. 50 miles south of Cairo. It was not until 1928 that an analysis was made, but then C. H. Desch determined that one contained 7.50 percent nickel. Immediately thereafter, Wainwright began to publish his series of articles on

thunderbolts, meteorites, and omphaloi, among which was one entitled “Iron in Egypt”. In it, Wainwright revived von Lauth’s hypothesis (without citing this source), but used slightly different transliterations ... R. J. Forbes was a leader in refuting Wainwright’s hypothesis. “Wainwright.” he wrote, never brought forward one text in which *biḏ* must have meant iron, the old and recognized translation copper fits in just as well ... There is no reason not to suppose that the Egyptian thought their meteoric iron just a form of black unrefined copper and that they recognized its celestial origin much later ... Only when they had attained the full Iron Age and iron was smelted and worked in Egypt itself copper and iron were distinguished in separate metals”.

On copper in Egypt, see please among the “Additional Information”, which are given before References.

In the Glossary of the Encyclopedia of Ancient Egypt, [Bunson, 2014], we can find also mentioned the hematite. We can read that *ba'a en pet* is the *copper* from heaven, a meteorite”. And that *bia* is the resource called hematite.

Hematite in Egypt is also mentioned in [Harrell, 2012]. **hematite** (opaque brownish black to black with submetallic luster to silver gray with metallic luster [Fe_2O_3]). Used: rarely Pd to Pt/R. Source: no mine known, but both types of hematite are found in some igneous and metamorphic rocks in the Eastern Desert. Ancient name: probably *bia* but also *bia qesey*, and *beqes ankh* (Egyptian); *haematitis/haematites* (Greek/Roman).

In [Lacovara, 2016] it is told that the “ancient Egyptian word for iron is *bia em pet*, “copper from heaven,” so they knew both the extraterrestrial origin of meteoric iron and its relationship to the metal that could be produced from iron ores”. Then, as previously told we have “metal”, “copper”, “iron” and “hematite” for *bjā*.

Fig. 10 - High resolution scan of a pattern welded "Damascus" knife blade. Image Courtesy Fluzwup

Emperor Jahangir's meteorite blade

Now, let us pass from Egypt to China, but before some words about swords. Then, let us move through Mughal Empire.

Michelle Starr in her “Swords from the stars: Weapons forged from meteoric iron”, 2015, begins the article remembering that “Myth is littered with legendary swords. Durandal. Kusanagi. Legbiter. Excalibur. Joyeuse. Different factors make these weapons extraordinary, but if we had to choose, we'd definitely go for a sword made of meteoric iron. It's not as unusual an idea as it sounds. Throughout history, blades have been forged from chunks of metal fallen from the skies, often smelted together with terrestrial metals, then acid-etched, creating a patterned surface reminiscent of Damascus steel. This pattern is due to the nickel content in meteoric iron, which gives it a more silvery colour and sheen than terrestrial iron; folded together, they create an effect known as pattern welding”. The article continues explaining that “modern blacksmiths are still following the tradition”. One of them created a sword incorporating ataxite, a meteorite with a high proportion of nickel, at least 18 percent.

Then, we encounter Emperor Jahangir. He was the fourth emperor of the Mughal Empire, and ruled from 1605 until his death in 1627. “When a meteorite fell to Earth in April 1621 in Punjab, the local tax collector ordered” to search it. A piece of hot iron was found. “It was so hot; it was as if it had been taken out of a furnace. After a while it cooled off, the tax collector took it home, sealed it in a purse, and sent it to court.” Jahangir considered this meteoric iron as a gift from God and ordered his smiths to forge it into two swords and a dagger. To create these objects, the smiths mixed the meteoric iron with terrestrial iron.

Fig. 11 – Detail of pattern on the dagger. Courtesy Daderot for Wikipedia.

Sabri Ben-Achour, 2012, tells in the article entitled “Smithsonian Displays Mysterious Dagger From The Stars”, that “Some people said it [the dagger] had magical powers, and

Jahangir talks in his diary about how tough the blade was and how amazingly it cut. But that diary entry was the last anyone heard about it. The Mughal Empire rose and fell, its treasures were plundered or given away, and that was it... until after World War II". Then, the dagger arrived at the Smithsonian's Freer and Sackler galleries. By means of x-ray analysis techniques, it had been determined that it was forged from a meteorite that fell to earth from outer space.

From Egypt to China

BBC is reporting that the researchers who studies Tutankhamen's dagger [Comelli et al., 2016] stress that "Ancient Egyptians attached great significance to meteoritic iron for the production of fine ornamental or ceremonial objects" [BBC]. "They [the Ancient Egyptians] were aware that these rare chunks of iron fell from the sky already in the 13th [Century] BCE, anticipating Western culture by more than two millennia," they [the authors] write in their findings" [BBC]. For further information about meteoric iron found in ancient Near East and Mediterranean basin, see please the "Additional Information", before the references. But, what about the far East, for instance China? Before discussing the meteoric iron in China, let us consider [Rapp, 2013].

Many meteorites are composed of iron and nickel in a combination which is "nearly rustproof and easily recognized as metal. Meteoric iron is malleable and easily worked. Metallic meteorites were picked up and used by humans over 8000 years ago, before the Iron Age in the Old World. The prehistoric utilization of meteoric iron to fashion tools probably was worldwide, including the Arctic. Iron meteorites were prized in prehistoric America. The Aztec made knives from iron meteorites". Ref. [Rapp, 2013] is also stressing that ancient Sumerian texts mentioned the meteoric iron and called it the "fire from heaven". [Rapp, 2013] is providing several references.

As told in [Rapp, 2013], about the development and iron production in ancient China, an in-depth account is given by [Wagner, 1993, 1999]. Wagner reviewed the earliest use of iron in China and "suggests that, after the making of luxury weapons from meteoric iron during the Shang and early Zhou periods, the technique of solid-state iron ore smelting came to China by the eight century BCE from the west via Scythian nomads". Wagner tells also that "The earliest evidence of the use of iron in the area of Shang and Zhou culture consists of bronze axeheads of several kinds with cast-in edges of meteoritic iron ... There is room for the supposition that the iron parts were imports from elsewhere, but very little reason for it. More likely there were Chinese smiths in the Shang and early Zhou who hot-forged meteoritic iron and produced small edges to be cast into bronze axes and other edged weapons".

We have previously seen that, of Tutankhamen's dagger, an origin different from Egypt has been recently proposed (gift of Mitanni). For the Chinese axeheads, in the past, this

happened too. Donald B. Wagner, 1999, reported that Noel Barnard told in early 1970s the following: “I would simply observe here that the presence of meteoric iron in sharper form – particularly the FGA items (34-11) [Freer Gallery of Art] with dovetail cutting of the iron blade - must indicate an alien source of origin. Such articles have entered the Middle States’ area as the result of occasional contacts with nomadic peoples far to the west and beyond the present boundaries of China. There is no evidence at all which would allow us to assume that these meteoric iron blades could have been worked by Chinese artisans in Shang and Western Chou times.” Among Wagner’s comments we can find that “The bronze parts of these artefacts are clearly Chinese in Style, and there are also many similar Shang artefacts with cast-in jade cutting edges, ... More likely there were Chinese smiths in the Shang and early Zhou who hot-forgot meteoritic iron and produced small edges to be cast into bronze axeheads and other edged weapons, Meteoritic iron is usually fairly hard, and these bronze-iron weapons are likely to have been superior to weapons of bronze alone, but meteoritic iron is so rare that these must always have been uncommon luxury items.”

Pictures of “Two Chinese early Chou bronze weapons with iron blades” are given in “Here Are 5 Ancient Artifacts Crafted From Meteorites Thousands of Years Ago”, Ivan Petricevic, May 23, 2019, at the link <https://curiosmos.com>

“Several Chinese artifacts, including two early weapons, contain meteoritic iron. A broad axe with a spike made of bronze and a deeply rusted meteoritic iron blade, along with a dagger axe pointed with meteoritic iron, date from the early Chou Dynasty, about 3000 years ago. These weapons may have come from the tomb of Prince of Wei in Honan Province, Significantly, they were manufactured about 400 years before the general appearance of cast iron metallurgy in China. Because meteoritic iron varies in composition, and sometimes contains abundant impurities, it is notoriously difficult to forge. Nevertheless, there are many ancient and modern examples of ceremonial weapons made from meteoritic iron, the metal having been save for the swordsmith’s finest work” [Bevan and De Laeter, 2002].

Wagner noted that meteoric iron is hard, and then the bronze-iron weapons were superior to weapons of bronze alone. But the meteoric iron was rare and then these weapons were luxury items. “We do not know whether these smiths developed their techniques themselves or learned them from elsewhere. The probability of independent invention seems high, but I [Wagner] have no information at all on the use of meteoritic iron in early Central Asia”.

See please more details and descriptions of other Bronze-iron artifacts in the book by Wagner, at the following link <http://donwagner.dk/EARFE/EARFE.html>

Layers on the bronze blades

Qiu Lianghui (2013), in the “Metallurgical technology in Ancient China”, tells us about the bronze blades covered by layers of iron. “During the Zhou and Shang Periods, bronze weapons with iron blades were used. Two of these are kept in the Freer Gallery: a battle axe with an iron blade and a bronze dagger axe with a horizontal iron blade. Dating from the end of the Shang or the beginning of the Zhou dynasty, they were unearthed in Junxian, Henan in 1931. Based on this evidence, some scholars in China and abroad have claimed that Chinese iron smelting began during the Shang dynasty. The bronze battle axe with an iron blade excavated from the Shang ruins at Gaochen, Hebei, in 1972 further strengthened this argument. Through strict scientific evaluation, based on the crystal characteristics (the laminar distribution of the nickel content) of the siderite (formed in astronomical bodies by slow cooling of only several degrees every 10,000 years), [Qiu Lianghui] identified an essential distinction between artificially smelted iron and meteoric iron. [Qiu Lianghui] determined that these implements are made of meteoric iron layered with nickel which was forged onto the blades of bronze implements. This evidence refutes the claim that iron smelting began in China during the Shang dynasty. Tests on the bronze battle axe with an iron blade which was discovered in a Shang tomb in Pinggu, Beijing, in 1976 reveal that it is also made of meteoric iron. These implements show that meteoric iron was used in China before the Iron Age and that people could distinguish between iron and bronze. Because siderite is quite rare, it was appropriate to forge it onto the blades of bronze weapons”. [Qiu Lianghui, 2013]

“The earliest historical record shows that the use of meteoric iron preceded the technology of iron smelting elsewhere as well. Iron implements containing nickel forged from meteoric iron have been unearthed from tombs dating from before the Egyptian dynasties. The Assyrians and Babylonians called iron ‘parzillu’; the Sumerians and Chaldeans called it ‘barsa’; the Hebrews, ‘barzel’; and the Egyptians, ‘ba-en-pet’. These ancient names all mean ‘metal from heaven’, which suggests that the earliest iron implements used by man were all made from meteoric siderite. Therefore, we cannot simply identify the human use of iron implements as the beginning of iron smelting. Only after men had mastered iron smelting technology could they produce numerous iron implements, thus entering the iron Age”. [Qiu Lianghui, 2013]

“China mastered iron smelting technology during the Spring and Autumn periods. This claim is supported not only by historical documents, but also by an increasing number of Spring and Autumn iron implements.” [Qiu Lianghui, 2013]

Xia Dynasty (<i>unconfirmed</i>)	(ca. 2100–1600 B.C.)
Shang Dynasty	(ca. 1600–ca. 1050 B.C.)
Zhou Dynasty	(ca. 1050–256 B.C.)
Western Zhou	(ca. 1050–771 B.C.)
Eastern Zhou	(ca. 771–256 B.C.)
Spring and Autumn Period	(770–ca. 475 B.C.)
Warring States Period	(ca. 475–221 B.C.)
Qin Dynasty	(221–206 B.C.)
Qin Shihuangdi	221–210 B.C.
Er Shi	210–207 B.C.
Han Dynasty	(206 B.C.–220 A.D.)

List of Rulers in China, Courtesy https://www.metmuseum.org/toah/hd/chem/hd_chem.htm

Shang and Zhou

“The Shang Dynasty is the earliest ruling dynasty of China to be established in recorded history, though other dynasties predated it. The Shang ruled from 1600 to 1046 B.C. and heralded the Bronze Age in China” - <https://www.history.com/topics/ancient-china/shang-dynasty> and “The Zhou dynasty was a Chinese dynasty that followed the Shang dynasty and preceded the Qin dynasty. The Zhou dynasty lasted longer than any other dynasty in Chinese history (790 years)” - https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Zhou_dynasty

Meteoric Iron and Amulets

In [Wagner, 1993, 1999], we find stressed the use of meteoric iron for luxury weapons, like the Tutankhamun's dagger indeed. However, we could imagine the meteoric iron used also for small objects, such as amulets.

Tibetan Thokcha are tektites and meteorites which serve as amulets. Typically high in iron content, these are traditionally believed to contain a magical and protective power. “The use of meteoric iron has been common throughout the history of ferrous metallurgy.

Historically, thokcha were prized for the metallurgical fabrication of weapons, musical instruments, and sacred tools, ... Writer Robert Beer regards meteoric iron as "the supreme substance for forging the physical representation of the vajra or other iron weapons." It was believed that these amulets had been tempered by the celestial gods before falling to earth. Beer describes the metal falling from space as a metaphor for "the indivisibility of form and emptiness." <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Thokcha>

Thokcha is composed of two words which means "above, primordial, first, thunderbolt", and "iron, metal". Thokcha is therefore the "original iron" or the "thunderbolt iron." Also G. A. Wainwright, in his study of ancient Egypt, pointed out a link of the meteoric iron with thunderbolt. Thunderbolt is giving rise to flint and meteorites containing iron.

Hongshan Meteorite Iron?

In searching on the web for pictures of Chinese artifacts made of meteoric iron, I was surprised to find Chinese artifacts in the style of Hongshan Culture for sale at low cost, very low cost, if we consider the price of the bulk material (meteorites) and work to create these modern pieces.

“The Hongshan culture (simplified Chinese: 红山文化; traditional Chinese: 紅山文化; pinyin: Hóngshān wénhuà) was a Neolithic culture in the Liao river basin in northeast China. Hongshan sites have been found in an area stretching from Inner Mongolia to Liaoning, and dated from about 4700 to 2900 BC. The culture is named after Hongshanhou (simplified Chinese: 红山后; traditional Chinese: 紅山後; pinyin: Hóngshān hòu), a site in Hongshan District, Chifeng. The Hongshanhou site was discovered by the Japanese archaeologist Torii Ryūzō in 1908 and extensively excavated in 1935 by Kōsaku Hamada and Mizuno Seiichi”. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Hongshan_culture

On the web, I found an “Old Chinese China Hongshan Culture Meteorite Iron Hand-Carved Big Dipper Statue” on sale. We can see the Big Dipper asterism and what could be the W of Cassiopeia in the images shown in the web page. It seems also that a circle was carved to represent the fact that the stars of the Big Dipper are circumpolar stars. Seven stars indeed.

“Beidou 北斗 (lit. "Northern Dipper) is the common Chinese name for the Big Dipper. Tiangang 天罡 and Tiangangxing 天罡星 (with tian 天 "sky; h/Heaven" and xing 星 "star; heavenly body") both mean "Big Dipper; (esp.) handle of the Big Dipper" – and are the second of the 108 Stars of Destiny in the Water Margin”, as told at en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Bugang - “Cassiopeia lies across two of the quadrants symbolized by the Black Tortoise of the North (北方玄武, Běi Fāng Xuán Wǔ), The White Tiger of the West (西方白虎, Xī Fāng Bái Hǔ) and Three Enclosures (三垣, Sān Yuán), that divide the sky in traditional Chinese uranography”.

en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Cassiopeia_in_Chinese_astronomy

We can find also “China Hongshan culture Meteorite iron Big Dipper ball loong dragon hook stone” for instance. So, it would be interesting to know if these objects have been copied from neolithic, or more recent, Chinese originals, or they are simply based on artistic imagination.

The Nine Stars of the Big Dipper

The importance of the stars of the Northern and Southern Dipper is stressed in [Pankenier, 2011]. And we can find these stars also mentioned in the Chinese Theology, https://www.wikiwand.com/en/Chinese_theology , then we have not to be surprised to find these asterisms depicted on Chinese artifacts.

News of 2006 [China.org, 2006] , www.china.org.cn/english , tells that “A neolithic stone carving of the Big Dipper star formation has been found on Baimiaozi Mountain near Chifeng City in northwest China's Inner Mongolia Autonomous Region, according to experts”. The stone carving was discovered by Wu Jiakai, a researcher in literature and history. On the stone there are carved 19 stars. “The representation of the Big Dipper is on the north face of the stone”. "The stone was carved by neolithic dwellers," said Gai Shanlin, researcher with the Inner Mongolia Institute of Cultural Relics and Archaeology (IMICRA) and an expert in stone carving. ... Apart from the Big Dipper, Wu also found some "unexplained images" on the stone. He thinks they may depict ancient gods, such as the god of the sun and the god of horses.”

And in the news we can find also told that “Many neolithic jade articles from the Hongshan Culture -- such as a dragon with a pig's mouth and a cloud-shaped pendant -- have already been unearthed around Baimiaozi Mountain. The Hongshan Culture was an aboriginal culture that existed in northern China about 6000 years ago. Tala believes the discovery will contribute to knowledge about the origin and spread of Hongshan Culture”.

Navigating in Religious Life

Yiwen Li, 2020, is proposing a discussion entitled "Navigating Voyages in Real and Religious Life: The Big-Dipper Belief and Shipbuilding in Premodern China". In the text we find that in Daoism, "the visualization of stars was a way to "enable the adept to integrate self and Dao, body and cosmos on a higher level". Shih-shan Susan Huang, 2012, divides the images of the visualization of stars into four subcategories: narrative illustrations of the adept's journeys to the Big Dipper, imaginary star maps, stars in the human body, and star divinities as iconic form. She emphasizes particularly that "the common ground for these images highlights the role of the Big Dipper, one of the most important constellations in Chinese visual culture" (Huang 2012, p. 38)." (Li, 2020).

"The Big-Dipper images in navigation maps and those in the religious context are different in two significant aspects. First, the Big Dipper images in the religious context were sometimes comprised of nine stars instead of seven, while the nine-star image was never seen in navigation maps or ships. The nine-star Big-Dipper image existed as early as 1116 and kept appearing in Daoist images afterward. The eighth star, the Fu star, is the companion of the sixth star, and the ninth star, the Bi star, is near the handle of the Dipper. While the Fu star is discernible under very particular conditions - on specific days with a very clear sky - the Bi star is entirely invisible. A well-accepted belief among the adepts says: "those who manage to glimpse these two stars are rewarded with a prolongation of three hundred years of life for the eighth and six hundred years for the hidden ninth star" (Mollier 2008, p. 162)." (Li, 2020).

Fig. 12 - Shang-di, aka, the Jade Emperor, Stone carving from the Wuliang Shrine, ca. 150 CE. Courtesy <https://planetandepoch.com/> , adapted from [Major, 1993]. The same scheme of stars is given in [Pankenier, 2011]. Note that "The eighth star, the Fu star, is the companion of the sixth star, and the ninth star, the Bi star, is near the handle of the Dipper." (Li, 2020).

Fig. 13 – The Big Dipper and the Pole Star (Stella Polare), year 150, Zhenjiang, Jiangsu province, simulated by Stellarium.

Not only on stones. In “Ancient Big Dipper temple found in Central China”, (see for instance link http://www.kaogu.cn/en/News/New_discoveries/2018/0403/61554.html or link http://www.china.org.cn/arts/2018-03/30/content_50776890.htm), it is told that “Archaeologists in central China's Henan Province have discovered ruins dating back around 5,000 years, believed to be a temple in the shape of the Big Dipper”. The excavation at the Qingtai ruins in the city of Xingyang is considered one of the “top five archaeological discoveries in the province in 2017”. “Nine ceramic pots are laid out in the shape of the Big Dipper, with a round sacrificial altar at the eastern side, said Wei Qingli, a researcher with Zhengzhou cultural heritage institute. In ancient China, the Big Dipper was composed of seven "visible" stars and two "invisible" ones, probably nearby Messier objects. ... “The discovery shows that people had some astronomic knowledge and an established ritual ceremonial pattern in the shape of the Big Dipper," Wei said. Qingtai ruins are one of the examples of Neolithic Yangshao culture”.

Mizar and Alcor

“Mizar and Alcor are two stars forming a naked eye double in the handle of the Big Dipper (or Plough) asterism in the constellation of Ursa Major. Mizar is the second star from the end of the Big Dipper's handle, and Alcor its fainter companion. The traditional name Mizar derives from the Arabic المنزر *mi'zar* meaning 'apron; wrapper, covering, cover'.

Alcor was originally Arabic سها Suhā/Sohā, meaning either the ‘forgotten’ or ‘neglected’ one; notable as a faintly perceptible companion of Mizar. Mizar, also designated Zeta Ursae Majoris (ζ Ursae Majoris, abbreviated Zeta UMa, ζ UMa), is itself a quadruple system and Alcor, also designated 80 Ursae Majoris (80 UMa), is a binary, the pair together forming a sextuple system. The whole system lies about 83 light-years away from the Sun, as measured by the Hipparcos astrometry satellite.” https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Mizar_and_Alcor

Supernova

An interesting discussion about the number of stars composing the Big Dipper asterism is given in the article entitled “There are several Big Dipper stars, seven or nine, the views of ancient people five thousand years ago are very different from today”, In *inf.news*, <https://inf.news/en/culture/>, it is told that the ancestors distinguished north, south, east, and west through the Big Dipper. “However, the number of the Big Dipper stars with such an important position in the development history of Chinese civilization has been unclear. The literature generally records that they are composed of the seven stars "Tianshu, Tianxuan, Tianji, Tianquan, Yuheng, Kaiyang, and Yaoguang".” It is told in the pre-Qin literature that "Big Dipper nine stars, seven see (present) two hidden", so is the Big Dipper nine or seven? Evidence was found in the Shuanghuaishu ruins, one of the “Top Ten New Archaeological Discoveries in China in 2020”.” (See the article archived at <https://archive.ph/1Ayyc>).

The article describes in detail these ruins. “In the front porch of the largest house [of the archaeological site], archaeologists discovered nine strange clay pots, seven of which were large and two were small. On top of the nine clay pots, there is a complete elk skeleton facing south and facing the doorway. ... Gu Wanfa, director of the Zhengzhou Institute of Cultural Relics and Archaeology,” explained “the figure composed of elk and nine clay pots. It turns out that this is the "Big Dipper Nine Stars" recorded in the history books of the Pre-Qin Dynasty”. A picture of the site is also given in the article.

The article is also mentioning a supernova in the Big Dipper. “ "He Tu" records: "The Emperor Huang ruled, and Jing Xing was seen in the Big Dipper." The ancients named the supernova Jing Xing. During the Huang Emperor period, Jing Xing may have appeared, bursting out with shining light, shining like the Big Dipper stars”. The same could have been happened in very ancient times. “The ancestors mistakenly thought it was one of the Big Dipper stars. Since the supernova explosion ended soon, the later generations would not be able to observe it”. <https://archive.ph/1Ayyc>

Fig. 14 - Pig-dragon. Image Courtesy Sailko for Wikipedia Wikimedia

Cultura di hongshan (neolitico), oggetto rituale zhulong (dragone-maiale) in nefrite, da lianing, 3500 ac. ; Pièce jue en forme de dragon.

Vraisemblablement région de Hongshan, Liaoning. Jade, H. 15,3 cm. Vers 4700-3000 avant l'ère commune. Paris Musée National des Arts Asiatiques - Guimet. Ref. Danielle Elisseeff, 2008. Manuels de l' Ecole du Louvre: Art et archéologie : La Chine. Du Néolithique à la fin des Cinq Dynasties (960 de notre ère). Notice 7, page 124-125. "Amulette en forme de larve au museau vaguement porcin", Roberto Ciarla. L'armée éternelle, National Geographic, 2005, p. 22.

Pig-dragon

Besides the stars of Big Dipper on meteorites, among the modern artifacts available on the web, we have also “9.2” Antique China Neolithic Age Hongshan Culture Carved Meteorite Beast Statue”, and “Large magnetic field black-skinned magnetite iron meteorite Hongshan Jade Pig Dragon pendant handle” or “ 9.4” Old Neolithic Age Hongshan Culture Meteorite carved inlay Turquoise Statue”. “Hongshan culture antique jade black iron meteorite tortoise statue” and “Hongshan culture antique jade collection iron black meteorite cicada”. In fact, Pig-Dragon and Cicada has been carved in jade by neolithic Hongshan people.

The “secret” Hongshan culture

On September 12, 2018, Natalia at <http://natalymaster.com/en/2018/09/12/the-secret-huangshan-culture/> wrote that “There is one more secret place in the northeast of China, about which there are a lot of legends. It is as famous as the Himalayas in Tibet. An ancient civilization engendered 6-7 thousand years ago in the Huanghe river basin is nowadays famous by its Hongshan Neolithic culture. ... Hongshan Culture being the culture of daily existence disappeared thousands years ago. But its reminiscence has left its mark not only in the Celestial Empire... The secret articles of the masters of this

civilization are still admired. They are argued about. They are investigated. People look for the answers to the undiscovered questions... *It is Hongshan culture that gave birth to many greenstone and meteorite articles. Especially aerosiderite articles (iron-stone meteorite alloys)*". <https://archive.is/Xa7ar>

“Aerosiderite: A meteorite consisting mainly of nickel and iron; an iron meteorite. Also: the mineral of which this is composed; meteoric iron. Compare "aerolite", "aerosiderolite". Now usually shortened to siderite”, as told by the web site <https://www.lexico.com/definition/aerosiderite> .

Natalia shows “a famous sample of Hongshan culture piece of work”, called the Sun-god. “Even scientists and investigators still do not know how this deity appeared. Some of them think they speak about Sun-god (like Ra in Ancient Egypt). Other scientists are sure that the history of the figure appearance is connected with shamanism”.

“It is no coincidence that there are a lot of meteorite articles in Hongshan culture. Hongshan people were very passionate about space bodies and the places of their falling”. And here an answer by Natalia to Noah. “I think in China you can easily find products in the Hongshan culture style. Of course, these will not be ancient figures (but there are many more modern examples). As for collectibles. In northeastern China, near historical Manchuria ... there are many so-called “jade meteorites.” Unfortunately, real collectible figurines (true Hongshan, 2,000-7,000 years old) are unlikely to be available to the simple buyer. But today in the Chinese market there are a lot of modern copies called meteorite jade, made in the style of Hongshan culture”.

On the web then, we can find modern objects in the style of Neolithic Hongshan. The fact that this Chinese culture used “jade meteorites” or iron meteorites is not stressed in [Peterson et al., 2010, Childs-Johnson, 1991, Wagner et al., 2013, Hosner et al., 2016, Drennan et al., 2017] for instance. However, according to Natalia’s words, ancient artifacts made of siderite exist.

Fig. 15 - Hongshan Culture, Inner Mongolia, 1973. One of earliest dragon images found in China. National Museum: China Through the Ages, exhibit 1. Complete indexed photo collection at WorldHistoryPics.com. 2011. www.flickr.com Courtesy of the author, Gary Todd. And also “Neolithic jade dragon, H. 26 cm, Hongshan Culture, Inner Mongolia, excavated in Sanxingtala, Ju Ud (act. Chifeng), 1973. National Museum of China, Beijing ” - caption of the image at <https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/>

The C-dragon

In https://www.chinadaily.com.cn/culture/2015-01/04/content_19231432.htm , it is stressed that “China's mysterious Neolithic Hongshan culture is considered one of the earliest and most advanced ancient civilizations discovered to date. The Hongshan inhabited lands in northeastern China, between Inner Mongolia and today's Liaoning and Hebei provinces from around 4700 to 2900 BC. The name "Hongshan" is derived from Hongshan Mountain in Chifeng, ideally located between the Yellow River basin and the northern steppes of Inner Mongolia's autonomous region bordering Liaoning province. Though little is known about their daily lives, the Hongshan have become world famous for their exquisite jade sculptures, prestigious concentration of funeral offerings and unique ritual centers. Their patterns of technology and worship appear to have had an influence on later Chinese traditions”. [Liu Xiongfei, 2015]

Fig. 16 - The amulet - Jade Gallery, Aurora Museum, Pudong, Shanghai.

<https://www.flickr.com/photos/101561334@N08/22267459958/> Courtesy Gary Todd

References on Hongshan Culture are given in [Peterson et al., 2010, Childs-Johnson, 1991, Wagner et al., 2013, Hosner et al., 2016, Drennan et al., 2017]. Hongshan jades according to type, style and material are given in [Childs-Johnson, 1991]. Pig-Dragon and C-Dragon are discussed in detail.

In her web page, Natalia stresses that “Hongshan culture will remain one of the most important historical cycles in China life. You will certainly meet the pieces of this history in any part of the Celestial Empire. In the form of figures first of all. *By the way, it is China, Hongshan, where the cult of Dragon was born.* In Hongshan articles there are many figures with dragon heads. Sometimes they are specific, with circinated tails”.

Rituals

In [Johnson and Tyldesley, 2014] it is told that “Most of the early examples of iron in Egypt are obviously symbolic or ritual artefacts”. “All the examples were recovered from graves, and therefore are likely to have some ritual connection with the funeral and/or rebirth of the deceased”. Let us remember once more the adze of iron in association with the Opening of the Mouth ceremony. The article stresses that “iron was allowed an important role in this ceremony because meteoritic iron was associated with meteors and thunderbolts; powerful natural phenomena whose own inherent power might increase the potency of the ritual”. In the case of the adze, used as a ritual implement, the meteoric iron suggests “a link to the stars themselves, while the constellation Ursa Major (aka ‘The Plough’ or ‘Big Dipper’) forms the shape of the adze, the stars in Ursa Major were considered to be ‘imperishable’ stars, the name used by the ancient Egyptians for stars not seen to set or rise because of their proximity to the northern celestial pole. Dead and reborn kings were identified with these special stars”. Article [Johnson and Tyldesley, 2014]) continues telling that meteorites may have played a more direct role in state religion and mentions the ‘Benben Stone’, the shining stone, worshiped in the temple of the sun god Re at Heliopolis.

In Egypt, the stars of the Big Dipper had been linked to iron and rituals, but in China, as shown by the "Big Dipper Nine Stars" at the 5,000-year-old Qingtai Ruins in Zhengzhou, the stars seem being the focus of a specific ritual. In fact, as stressed in [Pankenier, 2011], archaeology shows that the use of astronomical alignments representing the circumpolar nightly sky, was “firmly established by the formative period of Chinese civilization in the early 2nd millennium BCE”. Moreover, “the cosmological identification of the imperial center with the celestial Pole and an intense focus on the circumpolar ‘skyscape’ are manifested in the highly symbolic orientation of early imperial capitals” [Pankenier, 2011].

A study about the role of meteoric iron for Chinese rituals is under development.

Dream Pool Essays

Of ancient China we have information from the Dream Pool Essays. It “was an extensive book written by the Chinese polymath and statesman Shen Kuo (1031–1095), published in 1088 during the Song dynasty (960–1279) of China. Shen compiled this encyclopedic work while living in forced retirement from government office, naming the book after his private estate near modern Zhenjiang, Jiangsu province. The Dream Pool Essays was heavily reorganized in reprint editions by later Chinese authors from the late 11th to 17th centuries. ... The Dream Pool Essays covers a range of topics including discoveries and advancements in Traditional Chinese medicine, mathematics, astronomy, science and technology, optics, architecture and civil engineering, metallurgy, and early archaeology.

Observations of the natural world included those of wildlife, meteorology, hypotheses advancing early ideas in geomorphology and climate change based on findings of petrification and natural erosion, and strange recorded phenomena such as the description of an unidentified flying object.” From the item of Wikipedia, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Dream_Pool_Essays

In [Hamblyn, 2011], it is told that the Dream Pool Essays is a “sprawling collection” of more than five hundred entries on subjects including mathematics, astronomy, geology and botany. “Medieval Chinese technology was extraordinarily advanced”. According to the scientist and historian Joseph Needham (1900-95), “the world’s first description of a magnetic compass,” is contained in the Dream Pool. From [Hamblyn, 2011] let us see how the Dream Pool is describing the Pole Star and the meteorite fall.

“The Pole Star: Before Han times it was believed that the pole star was in the centre of the sky, so it was called Chi hsing (‘Summit star’). Tsu Kêng-Chih found out with the help of the sighting-tube that the point in the sky which really does not move was a little more than 1° away from the summit-star. In the Hsi-Ning reign-period (+1068-1077) I accepted the order of the emperor to take charge of the Bureau of the Calendar. I then tried to find the true pole by means of the tube. On the very first night I noticed that the star which could be seen through the tube moved after a while outside the field of view. I realized, therefore, that the tube was too small, so I increased the size of the tube by stages. After three months’ trials I adjusted it so that the star would go round and round within the field of view without disappearing. In this way I found that the pole-star was distant from the true pole some what more than 3° . We used to make diagrams of the field, plotting the positions of the star from the time when it entered the field of view, observing after nightfall, at midnight, and early in the morning before dawn. Two hundred of such diagrams showed that the ‘pole-star’ was really a circumpolar star. And this I stated in my detailed report to the emperor.” [Hamblyn, 2011]

Fig. 17 - The Pole Star (Stella Polare), year 1088, Zhenjiang, Jiangsu province, simulated by

Stellarium.

Fig. 18 - The Pole Star (Stella Polare), 1600 BC, Zhenjiang, Jiangsu province, simulated by Stellarium. The star was far from the pole, but Kochab was closer.

“Meteorite Fall: In the 1st year of the Chih-Phing reign period (+1064), there was a tremendous noise like thunder at Chhang-chou about noon. A fiery star as big as the moon appeared in the south-east. In a moment there was a further thunderclap while the star moved to south-west, and then with more thunder it fell in the garden of the Hsü family in the I-hsing district. Fire was seen reflected in the sky far and near, and fences in the garden round about were all burnt. When they had been extinguished, a bowl-shaped hole was seen in the ground, with the meteorite glowing within it for a long time. Even when the glow ceased it was too hot to be approached. Finally the earth was dug up, and a round stone as big as a fist, still hot, was found, with one side elongated. Its colour and weight were like iron. The governor, Chêng Shen, sent it to the Chin Shan temple at Jun-chou, where it is till kept in a box and shown to visitors.” [Hamblyn, 2011].

After reporting these same passages from the Dream Pool, in Needham and Ronan, 1978, it is told that “Meteorites had many other names in Chinese books besides the *yün* already mentioned, or *yün shih*. Very early on they they were called *thien chhuan*, ‘hounds of heaven’. Moreover, as in other civilizations, meteorites were sometimes confused with axes of the Neolithic period: in AD 660 a meteorite presented to the emperor was called ‘the stone of the thunder-god’, and other names were ‘the thunder-god’s ink block’ or ‘thunder lumps’.”

Additional Information

In [Rickard, 1941], we can find some references in the **Latin literature about meteorites.**

– VI – “The celestial origins of meteorites was recognized at an early date. Livy makes note of several showers of stones that fell from the air, like hail, in 654 BC. Chinese records mention a fall of meteorites in 644 BC. Among the most famous of ancient meteorites is the one that fell in 466 BC at Aegospotami, in Thrace, as is recorded on the Parian marble (now in the Ashmolean Museum, at Oxford). It is mentioned by Pliny also. Plutarch, in his life of Lucullus, describes the fall of a meteorite at the moment when the Roman legions under Lucullus were about to engage the Macedonian army under Mithridates, in AD 73. “In the very instant before joining battle, without any perceptible alteration preceding, on a sudden the sky opened, and a large luminous body fell down in the midst between the armies, in shape like a hogshead, but in colour like melted silver, in so much that both armies in alarm withdrew” (1910, p.237). References to meteorites are to be found in Revelation (vi. 13; viii, 10; xii, 3, 4).”

In the article entitled “**Sacred meteorites** and various stories associated with them”, by Andrzej Kotowiecki, <http://pressmania.pl/sacred-meteorites/> , we can find that “in the history of antiquity, we have many examples of meteorites owned by temples as well as examples of their collection and worship as gifts from the gods. In the Artemision in Ephesus, one of the seven wonders of the ancient world, a large black stone that fell from heaven was stored. ... “. Many other meteorites are mentioned by Kotowiecki.

In [Schaaf, 2002], it is told that “A chariot-sized stone is supposed to have killed ten men in China in 616 BC. Meteorite falls and finds in China date back to before 2100 BC (though this is before the historical period), and iron meteorites were alloyed with bronze to make weapons there before 1000 BC. Formal records on meteorite falls and speculation on their cosmic origins began in China as early as 645 BC. ... Even earlier than the Chinese use of meteorite iron seems to be that of the Hittites, usually credited with the first successful smelting of iron, around 1400 BC. A list of treasures of a **Hittite** king in the sixteenth century BC mentions “**black iron of heaven from sky**”. More than three millennia later, the fantasy writer J. R. R. Tolkien tells the story of a hero with a sword “made of iron that fell from heaven as a blazing star”.

In discussing the “legs” from Hasanlu, Ref. [White Muscarella, 1988] tells the following. “If the legs were from a chair or throne, one may suggest that the Hasanlu legs belonged to a wood and iron throne, and thereby continued a long tradition. For we are reminded of the Hittite Old Kingdom Anitta text that mentions an iron throne as a precious royal object (Waldbaum 1978, 21, n.92). Whether the iron legs belonged to a statue of a human, the body of which was sculpted wood, is of course not possible to recognize (Hittite texts mention iron statues: Waldbaum 1978 ,21, 94)”.

From [Robinson, 1951] – **Artifact of Meteoric Iron** - “We may now examine what is known of meteoric iron artefacts in prehistoric times. Unfortunately the list is a short one, and is no doubt incomplete. After all, as the Eskimo worked and used meteoric iron with very primitive equipment, we cannot deny that prehistoric man may well have done the

same thing, indeed we have proof that this was so. First, we have the iron beads which Wainwright (1936, p. 7) found at Gerzah in Egypt, about fifty miles to the south of Cairo. ... In the XVIII-dynasty tomb of Tutankhamun were several iron objects, a dagger, miniature head-rest, an amuletic eye, and sixteen miniature implements (Lucas, 1948, p. 272). ... Certainly of meteoric origin is a small amulet which has a silver head and an iron blade. This amulet is from Deir el Bahari, in Egypt, and is of the XI-dynasty. ... Several other finds of early iron in Egypt have often been quoted, but as there appears to be considerable doubt about their origin and dating, it would be unwise to include them in our list. In one of the Royal Tombs of Ur in Mesopotamia, Sir Leonard Woolley found some fragments of iron (Peake, 1933, p. 641, and Desch, 1928). These fragments contained 10.9 per cent, of nickel, and were therefore of meteoric origin. There are two objects from Treasure L of Troy II or III, but doubt was expressed whether these pieces were really iron, and analyses were therefore carried out Hence, it is unwise to consider that the Treasure L find is of meteoric origin. It is also significant that artefacts of relatively low nickel iron have been recorded from period III of Alaca Hüyük. These are an iron pin with gold-plated head, Al/a, MC 34, and a fragment of a crescent plaque, Al/a, MC 33. Both objects have been analyzed with the following results ... In view of the above figures it is possible that a low-nickel meteoric iron is here in question. Przeworski (1939, p- 143) says that there were early finds of meteoric iron from a Tholos near Platamos, and at Mavro Spelio, but he does not comment on the nickel content. Peake (1933, p. 641) mentions that in 1927 a cube of iron was discovered at Knossos in Crete in a Middle Minoan grave dating from about 1800 b.c. It had evidently been regarded as a precious object, and is likely to be of meteoric iron. The same is probably true of the iron finger-ring, believed to date from 1550 b.c., found at Pylos in the Peloponnesus. In the case of artefacts of the lower nickel ranges, unless there is careful metallographic examination as well as the analyses, a certain confusion would appear possible because of the mineral pyrrhotite (an iron mineral which occurs in grains or massive form impregnating metamorphic or crystalline rocks).”

About **copper in Egypt**, see please Ref. [Johnsen, 2018)]. We can find that N41 was used for copper. “Copper, known to the ancient Egyptians as *ḥmt* or *bḏ* is a naturally occurring metallic element that forms thin, crumpled, sheet-like or small nugget formations in its native form. ... If iron had been used in the production of large numbers of objects anciently than it stands to reason that such objects would have been preserved in a similar manner to other artifacts and that archaeologists would be able to identify them in the archaeological record. Unfortunately, few such items exist. The primary evidence of iron use is found in the slag that remains from copper and bronze smelting operations. Small amounts of iron oxide were used as fluxing agents to process copper and separate it from its impurities in the smelting process. One other, often cited example of an iron artifact from New Kingdom Egypt is Tutankhamun’s iron dagger (JE 61585AB). However, the dagger is not necessarily an Egyptian product. It appears to have been a gift given by a

foreign, likely Hittite, dignitary or king. Furthermore the dagger is purportedly made of meteoric iron. In either case, the general use of iron as a material resource seems not to have taken root with in the technology of Egypt. Whatever the reason, the failure to develop and use iron as a resource put Egypt at a distinct technological disadvantage when compared to its neighboring Near Eastern kingdoms and is one of the possible causes for the downfall of Egyptian civilization during the Late Period and the success of foreign invaders like the Persians.”

let us move from Egypt to Central Asia, where we find the fearless king Geser. As we have previously told, J. R. R. Tolkien wrote of him and his sword.

In [Day, 2020], Geser and Kurkar are described. Geser “becomes an extraordinary alchemist by combining his skills as a smith with his inherited powers of sorcery. He creates many wonders in his smithy for his master, but for himself he forges an unbreakable **sword from celestial (meteoric) iron**. Geser prepares himself for his ultimate duel with his great enemy, Kurkar. However, he knows that his enemy cannot be slain until a huge iron mandala ring or talisman that is kept in the palace treasury is destroyed. This huge iron talisman contains the “life” or “soul” or Kardar and all ancestors. ...”

“The Epic of King Gesar[a] ... is an epic cycle, of Tibet and greater Central Asia, believed to date from the 12th century, that relates the heroic deeds of the culture hero Gesar, the fearless lord of the legendary kingdom of Ling (Wylie: gling). It is recorded variously in poetry and prose, through oral poetry performance, it is sung widely throughout Central Asia and North East of South Asia. ... The first printed version was a Mongolian text published in Beijing in 1716.” From Wikipedia

“There is no indication that **Tolkien** knew or was inspired by the tales of Geser and Kurkar, but both The Lord of the Rings and the stories of Geser share an ancient and widespread archetypal theme of kings as magician-smiths and ring lords” [Day, 2019].

In [Bellezza, 2014], we can find that “the priest and rules of Zhang Zhung were attired in sumptuous fur robes, and that they wore turquoise, patterned agates, and **meteoric iron talismans**, as well as brandishing many kind of weapons.” “Zhangzhung or **Shangshung** was an ancient culture and kingdom of western and northwestern Tibet, which pre-dates the culture of Tibetan Buddhism in Tibet. Zhangzhung culture is associated with the Bon religion, which in turn, has influenced the philosophies and practices of Tibetan Buddhism. ... Recently, a tentative match has been proposed between the Zhangzhung and an Iron Age culture now being uncovered on the Changtang plateau in northwestern Tibet.” <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Zhangzhung>

In [GUIDE], an **expert’s guide to meteorites** is given.

References

- 1) Alford, Alan F. (2010). Pyramid of Secrets. The Architecture of the Great Pyramid Reconsidered in the Light of Creational Mythology. Eridu Books. First Edition: February 2003. Eridu Books.
- 2) Alford, Alan F. (2004). The Midnight Sun. The Death and Rebirth of God in Ancient Egypt. Eridu Books.
- 3) Alford, Alan F. The Great Pyramid, https://old.world-mysteries.com/alford_GP.htm
- 4) Allen, James P. (2007). The Ancient Egyptian Pyramid Texts. By James P. Allen. ISBN: 9781589836785, 1589836782, 2007. Contributors: James P. Allen, Peter Der Manuelian.
- 5) Almansa-Villatoro, M. V. (2019). The Cultural Indexicality of the N41 Sign for bj3: The Metal of the Sky and the Sky of Metal. The Journal of Egyptian Archaeology, 105(1), 73-81.
- 6) Archaeology.wiki (2022). Tutankhamun's meteoric iron dagger: a royal gift from Mitanni? Link <https://www.archaeology.wiki/blog/2022/02/23/tutankhamuns-meteoric-iron-dagger-a-royal-gift-from-mitanni/>
- 7) Barras, Colin (May 4, 2020). Ancient Egyptians saw the sky as crumbling iron tub filled with water. NewScientist, www.newscientist.com/article/2242507-ancient-egyptians-saw-the-sky-as-crumbling-iron-tub-filled-with-water/
- 8) Bauval, R. G., and A.G. Gilbert (1994). The Adze of Upuaut: The Opening Of The Mouth Ceremony And The Northern Shafts In Cheops s Pyramid, Discussions in Egyptology 28, 1994.
- 9) Bauval, Robert. The "Giza Diagonal" and the "Horizon of Khufu": True or False?. Academia.edu
- 10) Bauval, R. (1999). Secret chamber: The quest for the hall of records. Century.
- 11) Ben-Achour, Sabri (2012). Smithsonian Displays Mysterious Dagger From The Stars. Metro Connection. <https://wamu.org/story/>
- 12) BBC <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-middle-east-36432635>
- 13) Bellezza, John Vincent (2014). The Dawn of Tibet: The Ancient Civilization on the Roof of the World. Rowman & Littlefield, Aug 29, 2014
- 14) Bevan, Alex, and John Robert De Laeter (2002). Meteorites. A Journey Through Space and Time. UNSW Press. ISBN:9780868404905, 086840490X
- 15) Bjorkman, J. K. 1973. Meteors and meteorites in the ancient near east. Meteoritics & Planetary Science 8: 91– 132.
- 16) Broad, William J. (2011). Black-Market Trinkets From Space, The New York Times, <https://www.nytimes.com/2011/04/05/science/05meteorite.html>
- 17) Budge, Sir Ernest Alfred Wallis (1988). From Fetish to God in Ancient Egypt, Dover

Publications. ISBN:9780486258034, 0486258033

- 18) Budge, Sir Ernest Alfred Wallis (1904). *A Guide to the First and Second Egyptian Rooms Predynastic Antiquities, Mummies, Mummy-cases, and Other Objects Connected with the Funeral Rites of the Ancient Egyptians*. British Museum. Department of Egyptian and Assyrian Antiquities. Harry Reginald Hall.
- 19) Bunson, Margaret (2014). *Glossary of the Encyclopedia of Ancient Egypt*, Infobase Publishing.
- 20) Burke, John G. (1991). *Cosmic Debris - Meteorites in History*. University of California Press. ISBN:9780520073968, 0520073967
- 21) Cesnola Collection (Metropolitan Museum of Art), New York. *Handbook of the Cesnola Collection of Antiquities from Cyprus*, Sir John Linton Myres, 1914
- 22) Childs-Johnson, E. (1991). *Jades of the Hongshan culture: the dragon and fertility cult worship*. *Arts asiatiques*, 82-95.
- 23) China.org (2006). *Neolithic Stone Carving of Big Dipper Discovered*. Xinhua News Agency August 16. <http://www.china.org.cn/english/features/Archaeology/178148.htm>
- 24) Choi, Charles Q. (2022). *Heated Debate Rises Over Hints of Superconductivity Above Boiling Temperatures*. *Inside Science*. <https://www.insidescience.org/news/heated-debate-rises-over-hints-superconductivity-above-boiling-temperatures>
- 25) CNRS.FR <https://www.cnrs.fr/en/bronze-age-artifacts-used-meteoric-iron>
- 26) Comelli, D., D'Orazio, M., Folco, L., El-Halwagy, M., Frizzi, T., Alberti, R., Capogrosso, V., Elnaggar, A., Hassan, H., Nevin, A., Porcelli, F., Rashed, M.G. and Valentini, G. (2016), *The meteoritic origin of Tutankhamun's iron dagger blade*. *Meteoritics & Planetary Science* 51: 1301-1309. <https://doi.org/10.1111/maps.12664>
- 27) Construction Specifier (2018). *Engineer shares new theory on the construction of Egyptian pyramids*. Link: www.constructionspecifier.com
- 28) Day, David (2020). *The Ring Legends of Tolkien: An Illustrated Exploration of Rings in Tolkien's World, and the Sources that Inspired his Work from Myth, Literature and History*. Hachette UK, Oct 8, 2020
- 29) Day, David (2019). *A Dictionary of Sources of Tolkien: The History and Mythology That Inspired Tolkien's World*. Hachette UK.
- 30) Dash, Mike (2011). *Inside the Great Pyramid*. *Smithsonian Magazine* <https://www.smithsonianmag.com/travel/inside-the-great-pyramid-75164298/>
- 31) Drennan, R. D., Peterson, C. E., Lu, X., & Li, T. (2017). *Hongshan households and communities in Neolithic northeastern China*. *Journal of Anthropological Archaeology*, 47, 50-71.
- 32) Eyre, C. (2002). *The cannibal hymn: a cultural and literary study*. Liverpool University Press.
- 33) Farley, Peter R. (2011). *Where Were You Before the Tree of Life? Volume 2* Lulu Press.

ISBN:9781257373093, 1257373099

- 34) Faulkner, R.O. (1969). *The Ancient Egyptian Pyramid Texts*, Oxford University Press.
- 35) Folco, L., Di Martino, M., El Barkooky, A., D'Orazio, M., Lethy, A., Urbini, S., Nicolosi, I., Hafez, M., Cordier, C., van Ginneken, M. and Zeoli, A., 2010. The kamil crater in Egypt. *Science*, 329(5993), pp.804-804.
- 36) Folco, L.; M. Di Martino; A. El Barkooky; M. D'Orazio; A. Lethy; S. Urbini; I. Nicolosi; M. Hafez; C. Cordier; M. van Ginneken; A. Zeoli; A.M. Radwan; S. El Khrepy; M. El Gabry; M. Gomaa; A.A. Barakat; R. Serra; M. El Sharkawi (2010-10-04). "Kamil Crater (Egypt): Ground truth for small-scale meteorite impacts on Earth". *Geology*. Retrieved 2011-01-24.
- 37) Fortean Times Magazine, "A beautifully researched, thoughtful, and thought-provoking study... stands well against the very best work produced by the acknowledged experts". October 2003.
- 38) Francis Lee, A. M. (1816). *The Odes of Pindar*, A. M. Francis Lee, W. Miller, 1810, London.
- 39) Frontier Post (2018). Egypt archaeologist criticises pyramid void 'discovery'. The Frontier Post. Link: thefrontierpost.com
- 40) Fujioka, M., Ishimaru, M., Shibuya, T., Kamihara, Y., Tabata, C., Amitsuka, H., Miura, A., Tanaka, M., Takano, Y., Kaiju, H. and Nishii, J. (2016). Discovery of the Pt-Based Superconductor LaPt5As. *Journal of the American Chemical Society*, 138(31), pp.9927-9934.
- 41) Geggel, Laura (2020). Ancient Egyptian temple reveals previously unknown star constellations, Live Science. Link: <https://www.livescience.com/ancient-egyptian-star-constellations.html>
- 42) Graves-Brown, Carolyn Anne (2010). *The Ideological Significance of Flint in Dynastic Egypt (Volume 1)*. Thesis Submitted to University College London for the Degree of Doctor of Philosophy. Institute of Archaeology. University College London. June 2010
- 43) Greshko, Michael (2017) Mysterious Void Discovered in Egypt's Great Pyramid The cavity is the first major inner structure discovered in the pyramid since the 1800s. November 2, 2017. National Geographic. www.nationalgeographic.com
- 44) GUIDE. An expert's guide to meteorites. <https://www.christies.com/features/A-collectors-guide-to-meteorites-8231-1.aspx>
- 45) Hamblyn, Richard (2011). *The Art of Science: A Natural History of Ideas*, Pan Macmillan, 2011.
- 46) Harrell, James (2012). Gemstones. *UCLA Encyclopedia of Egyptology Journal*. <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/57f2d2sk#supplementa>
- 47) Hawass. Zahi (2003). *The Secret Doors Inside the Great Pyramid*. https://www.guardians.net/hawass/articles/secret_doors_inside_the_great_pyramid.htm archived web.archive.org

- 48) Hoare, Callum (2020). Egypt: Mystery of Great Pyramid's contents identified as experts to uncover hidden voids. Link : <https://www.express.co.uk/>
- 49) Hoare, Callum (2019). Egypt experts set sights on finding lost Pharaoh's remains in Great Pyramid. Link: <https://www.express.co.uk>
- 50) Hooper, Rowan (2011). 25 May 2011, First images from Great Pyramid's chamber of secrets. *New Scientist* – <https://www.newscientist.com/article/mg21028144-500-first-images-from-great-pyramids-chamber-of-secrets/>
- 51) Hosner, D., Wagner, M., Tarasov, P. E., Chen, X., & Leipe, C. (2016). Spatiotemporal distribution patterns of archaeological sites in China during the Neolithic and Bronze Age: An overview. *The Holocene*, 26(10), 1576-1593.
- 52) Huang, S. S. S. (2012). *Picturing the True Form: Daoist Visual Culture in Traditional China*. BRILL.
- 53) Jambon, A. (2017). Bronze Age iron: Meteoritic or not? A chemical strategy. *Journal of Archaeological Science*, 88, 47-53. DOI 10.1016/j.jas.2017.09.008
- 54) Johnsen, D. (2018). The relative value and role of copper within an Egyptian New Kingdom economic context: Using production, trade and use of copper as indicators of copper's value [Master's thesis, the American University in Cairo]. AUC Knowledge Fountain. <https://fount.aucegypt.edu/etds/706>
- 55) Johnson, Diane, and Joyce Tyldesley (2014). Iron from the sky. The Geological Society. <https://www.geolsoc.org.uk/Geoscientist/Archive/April-2014/Iron-from-the-sky>
- 56) Johnson, D., Tyldesley, J., Lowe, T., Withers, P. J., & Grady, M. M. (2013). Analysis of a prehistoric Egyptian iron bead with implications for the use and perception of meteorite iron in ancient Egypt. *Meteoritics & Planetary Science*, 48(6), 997-1006. <https://doi.org/10.1111/maps.12120>
- 57) Jurewicz, Joanna, Ewa Masłowska, Dorota Pazio-Wlazłowska (2020). *The Soul in the Axiosphere from an Intercultural Perspective, Volume Two*, Cambridge Scholars Publisher. ISBN:9781527550094, 1527550095
- 58) Kawae, T., Inagaki, Y., Wen, S., Hirota, S., Itou, D. and Kimura, T., 2020. Superconductivity in palladium hydride systems. *Journal of the Physical Society of Japan*, 89(5), p.051004.
- 59) Kotowiecki, Andrzej (2021). Sacred meteorites. <http://pressmania.pl/sacred-meteorites/> ,
- 60) Lacovara, Peter (2016). *The World of Ancient Egypt: A Daily Life Encyclopedia [2 Volumes]*. ISBN:9781610692304, 1610692306 . November 21, 2016, ABC-CLIO
- 61) Lehner, Mark (1985). Giza. A Contextual Approach to the Pyramids. *Archiv für Orientforschung* 32 (1985), pp. 136-158.
- 62) Lehner, Mark (1997). *The Complete Pyramids*, Thames & Hudson 1997, p. 29.
- 63) Li, Yiwen (2020). Navigating Voyages in Real and Religious Life: The Big-Dipper Belief and Shipbuilding in Premodern China. *Religions* 11, no. 8: 398.

<https://doi.org/10.3390/rel11080398>

- 64) Liu Xiongfei (2015). Top 10 fine relics of China Hongshan Culture were unveiled in Inner Mongolia. China Daily. www.chinadaily.com.cn or web.archive.org
- 65) Major, John S. (1993). *Heaven and Earth in Early Han Thought: Chapters Three, Four, and Five of the Huainanzi* (Suny Series in Chinese Philosophy and Culture). State University of New York Press; Illustrated edition (August 3, 1993). ISBN-10 : 0791415864 , ISBN-13 : 978-0791415863
- 66) Marchant, Jo (2013). Iron in Egyptian relics came from space Nature. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature.2013.13091>
- 67) MaterialsToday (2016). Scientists squeeze superconducting properties out of platinum. <https://www.materialstoday.com/electronic-properties/news/scientists-squeeze-superconducting-platinum/>
- 68) Matsui, T., Moriwaki, R., Zidan, E., & Arai, T. (2022). The manufacture and origin of the Tutankhamen meteoritic iron dagger. *Meteoritics & Planetary Science*. First published: 11 February 2022 <https://doi.org/10.1111/maps.13787>
- 69) Mercer, S. A. B. (1952). *The pyramid texts* (Vol. 1). 2020 Edition, Library of Alexandria.
- 70) Mercer, S. A. (1952). The "Ka" in the Pyramid Texts. *Archiv Orientalní*, 20(1), 194-196.
- 71) Mitchell, Daniel E. (2014). *Finding Your Benben Stone And Building Your Great Pyramid of Success*. ISBN:9781452515502, 1452515506. Balboa Press
- 72) Mollier, C. (2008). *Buddhism and Taoism face to face*. University of Hawaii Press.
- 73) Morishima, Kunishiro, Mitsuaki Kuno, Akira Nishio, Nobuko Kitagawa, Yuta Manabe, Masaki Moto, Fumihiko Takasaki, Hirofumi Fujii, Kotaro Satoh, Hideyo Kodama, Kohei Hayashi, Shigeru Odaka, Sébastien Procureur, David Attié, Simon Bouteille, Denis Calvet, Christopher Filosa, Patrick Magnier, Irakli Mandjavidze, Marc Riallot, Benoit Marini, Pierre Gable, Yoshikatsu Date, Makiko Sugiura, Yasser Elshayeb, Tamer Elnady, Mustapha Ezzy, Emmanuel Guerriero, Vincent Steiger, Nicolas Serikoff, Jean-Baptiste Mouret, Bernard Charlès, Hany Helal & Mehdi Tayoubi (2017). Discovery of a big void in Khufu's Pyramid by observation of cosmic-ray muons. *Nature*, 552(7685), pp.386-390.
- 74) Needham, Joseph and Ronan, Colin A. (1978). *The Shorter Science and Civilisation in China: Volume 2*. Cambridge University Press
- 75) Nibbi, A. (1977). Some remarks on copper. *Journal of the American Research Center in Egypt*, 14, 59-65.
- 76) Orcutt, Larry (2000). The Iron Plate in the Great Pyramid, in *Catchpenny Mysteries*, 2000. <http://www.catchpenny.org/iron.html>
- 77) Otto, E. (1960), *Das Ägyptische Mundöffnungsritual*, Wiesbaden,
- 78) Palgrave, Francis Turner (1851). *General relations of mediaeval Europe. The Carolingian empire. The Danish expeditions in the Gauls. The establishment of Rollo*. 1851. Parker.

- 79) Pankenier, D. W. (2011). The cosmic center in Early China and its archaic resonances. *Proceedings of the International Astronomical Union*, 7(S278), 298-307.
- 80) Peterson, C. E., Lu, X., Drennan, R. D., & Zhu, D. (2010). Hongshan chiefly communities in Neolithic northeastern China. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 107(13), 5756-5761.
- 81) Petricevic, Ivan (2019). Here Are 5 Ancient Artifacts Crafted From Meteorites Thousands of Years Ago. May 23, 2019, link <https://curiosmos.com/>
- 82) Qiu Lianghui (2013). Metallurgical technology in ancient China. In *Chinese Studies in the History and Philosophy of Science and Technology*. Editors: Fan Dainian, Robert S. Cohen. Springer Netherlands. 2013. ISBN:9789401587174, 9401587175
- 83) Rapp, George R. (2013). *Archaeomineralogy*, Springer Science & Business Media, Mar 9, 2013 - Science - 326 pages
- 84) Raub, Ch. J. (1984). Superconductivity of the Platinum Metals and Their Alloys - A Review Summarising the Published Scientific Data, *Platinum Metals Rev.*, 1984, 28(2), 63.
- 85) Rehren, Thilo, Tamás Belgya, Albert Jambon, György Káli, Zsolt Kasztovszky, Zoltán Kis, Imre Kovács, Boglárka Maróti, Marcos Martín-Torres, Gianluca Miniaci, Vincent C. Pigott, Miljana Radivojević, László Rosta, László Szentmiklósi, Zoltán Szőkefalvi-Nagy, 5,000 years old Egyptian iron beads made from hammered meteoritic iron, *Journal of Archaeological Science*, Volume 40, Issue 12, 2013, Pages 4785-4792, ISSN 0305-4403, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jas.2013.06.002>.
- 86) Rickard, T. A. (1941). The Use of Meteoric Iron. *The Journal of the Royal Anthropological Institute of Great Britain and Ireland*. Vol. 71, No. 1/2 (1941), pp. 55-66
- 87) Robinson, G. W. (1951). *Soils, their origin, constitution, and classification* (Vol. 71, No. 4, p. 328). LWW Available archive.org/
- 88) Robinson, Rick (2020). King Tut's Meteorite Dagger: It Came From Outer Space, Link <https://now.northropgrumman.com/king-tuts-meteorite-dagger-it-came-from-outer-space/>
- 89) Roth, Ann Macy (1993). Fingers, Stars, and the 'Opening of the Mouth': The Nature and Function of the ntrwj-Blades. *The Journal of Egyptian Archaeology*, Vol. 79 (1993), pp. 57-79. Egypt Exploration Society. Stable URL: <http://www.jstor.org/stable/3822158>
- 90) Schaaf, Fred (2002). *The Starry Room: Naked Eye Astronomy in the Intimate Universe*. Dover Publications. December 6, 2002 - ISBN-10 0486425533 - ISBN-13 978-0486425535
- 91) Schultz, Colin (2013). The Ancient Egyptians Had Iron Because They Harvested Fallen Meteors: Modern chemical analysis confirms that ancient Egyptians used iron from meteorites. *Smithsonian Magazine*. Link: www.smithsonianmag.com
- 92) SCI-A <https://www.scientificamerican.com/article/king-tut-s-dagger-is-out-of-this-world/>

- 93) SCI-NEWS (2013). 5,000-Year-Old Egyptian Artifacts Made from Meteoritic Iron, Confirms New Study. <http://www.sci-news.com/archaeology/science-egyptian-artifacts-meteoritic-iron-01323.html>
- 94) Sinclair, Andrea (2022). The Mitanni origin of a meteoric iron (blade) of a dagger of Tutankhamen. artisticlicenseorwhyitrustnoone.blogspot.com or <https://web.archive.org>
- 95) Sparavigna, Amelia Carolina (2016). The Word Satellite, Its Origin from Etruscan and Its Translation into Greek (January 29, 2016). PHILICA, Article 568, Jan. 2016, Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=2899407>
- 96) Sparavigna, Amelia Carolina (2025). The Egyptian Hieroglyph of the Crested Ibis, from the Cheops' pyramid (Akhet Khufu) to the Akhenaten's Glory of Aten. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14605094>
- 97) Spence, Lewis (1917). Myths and Legends of Ancient Egypt. David D. Nickerson & Company, 1917.
- 98) Starr, Michelle (2015). Swords from the stars: Weapons forged from meteoric iron. c|net. <https://www.cnet.com/pictures/swords-from-the-stars-weapons-forged-from-meteoric-iron/>
- 99) W-Alford, Wikipedia. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Alan_F._Alford, on October 11, 2021. or the page archived on March 10, 2022 at web.archive.org
- 100) Wagner, D. B. (1993). Iron and steel in ancient China (Vol. 9). Brill.
- 101) Wagner, D. B. (1999). The earliest use of iron in China. BAR International Series, 792, 1-9.
- 102) Wagner, M., Tarasov, P., Hosner, D., Fleck, A., Ehrich, R., Chen, X., & Leipe, C. (2013). Mapping of the spatial and temporal distribution of archaeological sites of northern China during the Neolithic and Bronze Age. *Quaternary International*, 290, 344-357.
- 103) Wainwright, G. A. (1932). Iron in Egypt, *The Journal of Egyptian Archaeology*. Vol. 18, No. 1/2, pp. 3-15. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3854899> or <https://www.jstor.org/stable/3854899>
- 104) Waldbaum, J. C. and James D. Muhly The first archaeological appearance of iron and the transition to the iron age. Chapter in *The coming of the age of iron*, Theodore A. Wertme. ed., Yale University Press, 1980, ISBN 978-0300024258
- 105) Whipple, Tom (2017). Mystery void found in Great Pyramid of Giza. *The Times*. Link: www.thetimes.co.uk/article/mystery-void-found-in-great-pyramid
- 106) White Muscarella, Oscar (1988). *Bronze and Iron. Ancient Near Eastern Artifacts in the Metropolitan Museum of Art*. Metropolitan Museum of Art (New York, N.Y.), Read for free. ISBN:9780870995255, 0870995251.
- 107) Yamazaki, D., D. Ikeshima, R. Tawatari, T. Yamaguchi, F. O'Loughlin, J.C. Neal, C.C. Sampson, S. Kanae & P.D. Bates (2017). A high accuracy map of global terrain elevations. *Geophysical Research Letters*, vol.44, pp.5844-5853, 2017 doi:

10.1002/2017GL072874

- 108) Zhang, H-Q. (2023). The Akhet environment depicted by the Pyramid Texts – A comparison to the Atlas Basin hydrology during the Green Sahara time, *International Journal of Hydrology*, 7(1), 27-44. <https://medcraveonline.com/IJH/IJH-07-00336.pdf> (archived)